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All the Papers in every Issue will be inducted in to the current Issue Official E-Book

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The manuscript should contain the following section in order:

1. TITLE

The title must be written briefly and clearly, and must show precisely the problem to be raised, not to provide a variety of interpretive opportunities, not to contain abbreviations that are not commonly used, not too long (no more than 15 words), Times New Roman, font size 14 pt.

2. THE AUTHOR NAME

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3. ABSTRACT

Abstract is along 150-250 words with a font size of 10 pt and Times New Roman fonts and the distance between single-spaced lines. If the article is in Greek, then the abstract must be written in Greek and English that is good and correct. If the article is in English, the abstract must be written in English only. The Abstract section must contain the core issues to be raised, the method of solving them, and the scientific findings obtained and conclusions. Abstracts for each language can only be written in one paragraph in a single column format.

Keywords: Written in English 2-5 words or groups of words

4. INTRODUCTION (12pt, Times New Roman)

The introduction must contain (in sequence) a general background, a state of the art as a basis for statements of scientific novelty from articles, statements of scientific novelty, and research problems or hypotheses. At the end of the introduction, the purpose of the article review must be written. In the format of scientific articles, literature review is not permitted as in the research report, but is manifested in the form of a state of the art study to show the scientific novelty of the article.

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The flow of research should be presented in this section complete with captions. Image captions placed as part of the image title (figure caption) are not part of the picture. The methods used in completing the study are written in this section.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION (12pt, Times New Roman)

The results and discussion contain scientific research findings and discussions. Write down scientific findings obtained from the results of research that has been done but must be supported by adequate data. The scientific findings referred to here are not the results of research data obtained. The scientific findings must be explained scientifically including: What scientific findings were obtained? Why did that happen? Why are trend variables like that? All these questions must be explained scientifically, not only descriptive, if necessary

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This section can be written in case there are certain parties need to be acknowledged, such as research sponsors. The acknowledgement must be written in brief and clear. In addition, avoid the hyperbole acknowledgment.

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f. Website

United Arab Emirates architecture. (n.d.). Retrieved June 17, 2010, from UAE Interact website: <http://www.uaeinteract.com/>

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Build a Nucleus in the Classroom with a simulation Program

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Abstract

This paper presents the study of nucleons of chemical elements with a simulation program and the creation of different chemical elements. Students in the first high school class took part in this experiment in the chemistry lesson.

For the experiment we used the University of Colorado simulation program. We created atoms by placing protons and neutrons in the nucleus studying the atomic and mass number and the half-life.

The atomic and mass number and their relationship were studied in every element we created with the Simulation program. We were able to observe on the working screen the size of the atom in relation to the nuclear particle we have placed in the nucleus and calculating the number of electrons around the nucleus in the atom. Adding neutrons and protons we were able to change the mass and atomic number. With this simulation experiment, students learn how the size of the nucleus changed with the number of protons. We were able to identify different Chemical elements according to the number of protons and neutrons of the nucleus of the element we created according to the mass and atomic number.

The main goal of the experimentation laboratory was to create new elements by integrating neutrons and protons into the nucleus. Students were able to understand the difference that the nuclei of elements show in relation to the number of protons and neutrons and understand the use of mass and atomic number as a key in to identifying chemical elements.

Key words : Protons, Neutrons, Atom, Chemical element

Introduction

The nucleus of an atom is a small, a very dense, and a round region which located in to the centre of an atom. It has two subatomic particles which are the protons and the neutrons. Protons are electrically positively charged ions having a mass of approximately one atomic mass unit (*amu*). So we say tht the mass of an atom is the mass of the nucleus. Neutrons are electrically neutral. This nucleus of every chemical element , which is made up of protons and neutrons, contains the majority of the atom's mass (except for common hydrogen which has only one proton).

The Protons

A proton is a subatomic particle of the nucleus with a positive electric charge. They are in the nucleus of every atom of a chemical element. Protons determine the atomic number of each chemical element. This number is also equal to the number of atomic electrons of the chemical element

and also determines the chemical properties of the element.

Protons have slightly less mass than neutrons but they have a much greater mass equal to 1,836 times that of electrons. So we can confidently say that all the mass of an atom of an element is concentrated in the nucleus. Protons and neutrons together are called nucleons in each element.

The name for "proton" comes from the Greek word meaning "first". Ernest Rutherford was the Physicist who dealt with the atoms of the elements and coined the term "proton" for the nucleus of the hydrogen atom in the year 1920.

The Neutrons

Neutrons are subatomic particles found inside the nucleus of every atom. Neutrons do not exist in the hydrogen atom whose nucleus contains a proton. Neutrons are electrically neutral, meaning they are not charged and have a mass that is slightly larger than a proton.

When neutrons are in the nucleus they are stable. But this does not happen when they are free outside the nucleus, then the neutrons have an average lifetime of about 1,000 seconds.

Neutrons, along with protons and electrons, make up the three basic particles found inside an atom. We know today that there are many more particles very important to the structure of the nucleus of the atom of each element. While protons carry a positive charge and electrons a negative charge, neutrons have no charge at all and could be said to be something like balancers (Simopoulou P. D.2008).

Isotopes are the atoms of the same chemical element which differ only in the number of neutrons so they have the same Z and different N and A. This was an important step of study and in the experiment we did with the simulation program in the laboratory. For example, carbon-12 contains 6 neutrons, while carbon-13 contains 7. James Chadwick discovered neutrons in 1932. That is, the nucleus contains 99.97279% of the total mass of the atom of the element. But the nucleus of the atom is so very small that if we magnified it by a trillion times it would be the size of the head of a pin.

So we can say that at about this magnification the electrons would orbit the nucleus at a distance that was a few meters. This means that the atom of an element as a whole in space could be the size of a fairly large room. (Simopoulos D. 2008).

Preparation

Before starting the experiment, the students studied the corresponding textbook theory related to the presentation of the atomic and mass number and to the creation of the atoms of the elements as they appear in the periodic table of the elements. The relationship between mass and atomic number and the significance of these numbers for chemical elements was analyzed. The students understood the importance of the numbers A, Z, N to determine the position of the elements in the periodic table and their properties. (Drougas V. 2021)

The program <https://phet.colorado.edu/> of the University of Colorado was used and the build-a-nucleus chemistry simulation program was chosen, which is provided free of charge and can be used by students from the computer lab. In the particular experiment we used the interactive whiteboard in the physics and chemistry laboratory of the school.

Emphasis was placed on understanding the ratio of protons and the number of electrons the atom of each element contains in its neutral state. Thus, a greater number of protons in the nucleus mean a greater number of electrons in the atom, so the atom will present a different number of layers and its atomic distance from the center of the nucleus will increase. (Drougas V. 2022)

This cannot be easily understood from the textbook presentation of it and we chose to use the proton and neutron nucleation simulation program to make the students aware of the importance of the number of protons and neutrons in the nucleus of the atoms of the elements.

The experiment

As mentioned in the introduction we used the simulation program of the University of Colorado in the United States. From the program we chose simulation in Chemistry and build-a-nucleus. With this option, students have the possibility to choose from the work screen to place neutrons and protons in the nucleus. Attention was given to the students noticing that the nucleus does not have the ability to take only neutrons or only protons except in the case of the Hydrogen atom. It was also observed that for a certain number of neutrons we can have a certain higher number of protons in the nucleus. (Spartali N. 2010). The number of protons will give us the number of electrons spinning in shells around the nucleus. Students are able to observe the corresponding cloud created by the movement of electrons around the nucleus, as shown in the following images resulting from the experiment.

At the same time, on the right of the screen, every time they place a certain number of neutrons or protons in the nucleus, they observe the change in the name of the element and the number A, Z which represents the identity of the chemical element they have created with the new nucleus. So students can relate the theory and meaning of the numbers A and Z and the relationship to the name and identity of the element. At the same time they can understand through the representation of the electron cloud the difference in the weight of the atom and the size and detect the different behavior of the elements in Chemistry.

Students also studied Decay β and observed the change in the nucleus of the element and thus the element itself

Examples from the classroom experiment are shown below.

Typical simulation results

The following photos show images of the simulation the students made in the program and key features of the simulation on the work screen.

The experiment of simulating the creation of atoms of elements from the nucleus was a teaching hour. In the next class the students answered questions related to the experiment related to the presentation of the theory as it is presented in the textbook of the first high school.

Presentation of the B Decay and change of the Cl35/17 to S 35/16

The representation of the layer model by simulation

Feedback

After the end of the experiment the students understanding the importance of the subatomic particles of the nucleus and the role of protons and electrons in the creation of the elements and their properties could have formed an important insight into the theory of the subatomic nucleus.

Explain how the changing the number of neutrons or protons affects the atomic number and isotope species.

Describe how different decays will change the nucleons in the nucleus and if that changes the symbol of the atom being shown and affects parameters like atomic number/atomic mass.

Predict the shell model depiction of an isotope based on the isotope symbol or name.

Find the isotope on the nuclide chart using the symbol, name, or the number of protons and neutrons.

Predict the outcome

Conclusions

With the experiment of simulating the creation of atoms of the chemical elements and the difference in their naming in relation to the number of protons and neutrons of the nucleus, students were able to understand the importance of atomic and mass number in chemistry. These numbers are very important to the identity of the chemical elements and their place in the periodic table.

The simulation program allowed the students to very easily experiment with creating chemical elements by changing the structure of the nucleus and observing how new elements are created. They were very easily able to relate the theoretical presentation of the textbook and understand the role of the nucleus in the creation of chemical elements.

It was also understood the position of protons and neutrons in the atom and their relationship with the electrons of a neutral atom as well as the relationship of the energy layers of the atoms of the elements based on the electronic structure and the energy positions of the electrons K,L,M,N... Relevant experiments in the school curriculum in the chemistry lesson can help students understand the essence of chemistry and the role of chemical elements in relation to their structure.

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The role of STEAM education in curriculum 5.0

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Abstract.

At the threshold of the Fifth Industrial Revolution, as the economy shifts to more knowledge-intensive industries, there is an urgent need to develop the skills of students who are the leaders of future technological advancements and therefore redesign the curriculum. It is widely accepted that children get more motivated for learning when they choose a subject at school. Therefore, the teacher's role is to present knowledge in an attractive and interesting way. Inspiring students is crucial for the learning process. This is a difficult problem for STEM education because many primary school teachers do not necessarily have good knowledge of science. Teachers cannot inspire their students when they do not feel enthusiastic about a teaching subject. A CERN pioneering program, "Playing with protons" was created to solve this problem.

Keywords: STEM education, CERN, creativity, curriculum 5.0

Introduction

Industry 5.0 offers many opportunities for academic institutions to advance to the next level. Faculty 5.0 should go along with Curriculum 5.0. In the new curriculum we need to incorporate learning about robotics, internet of things, augmented reality, smart materials but at the same time integrate non-technical subjects (such as project management, communication, arts, etc.) in order to develop transdisciplinary skills. It is also important to focus on questions of ethics, diversity, social inclusion, and sustainability (e.g. teaching the Sustainable Development Goals).

1. STEAM education in Curriculum 5.0

In this curriculum, STEM, as transdisciplinary approach, aims to promote research spirit, logical thinking and social skills. Recently, arts have also been incorporated into STEM teaching, making these projects even more creative and interesting. As a result, the STEM acronym is now becoming

STEAM (Land, 2013). Emphasis is placed on empirical and exploratory-discovery learning, autonomy and active participation of students, through trial and errors, in a series of interactive projects that incorporate the five fields of STEAM (Maslyk, 2016). The acquisition of basic skills through STEAM projects, prepares young people for the future, as STEAM learning is framed in the daily life of young people outside the classroom (Daugherty, 2013). STEAM Education has as its center the problem solving ideas. Furthermore, STEAM education stimulates students' attention by developing their abilities for expression, creativity, with innovation playing the most significant role (Aguilera & Ortiz-Revilla, 2021).

STEAM can be unplugged or make use of technology. Unplugged activities can be implemented without the use of computers and can be used to engage in computational thinking dimensions, embedding computer science concepts into the curriculum. (Curzon, 2013). It is very important to promote computational thinking in the classroom, which includes abstraction, algorithmic thinking, decomposition and pattern recognition (Hoyle & Noss, 2015). Computational thinking involves solving problems and designing systems, by drawing on the concepts fundamental to computer science (Wing, 2006).

Educational Technologies such as augmented/virtual reality, clickers" or key-pads", cloud computing, and internet of me can promote STEM education, through the adoption of innovative teaching strategies, like hands-on activities, mini- and remote labs, building models, etc.

2. Teacher Training on STEAM education

Training teachers on STEAM practices is an important issue. A research was conducted in Australia among pre-service primary school teachers by a chief scientist of Australia (Prinsley, Johnston, 2015). The research investigated beliefs regarding STEM in terms of importance, innovation, skills in future, and high-quality specialist teachers to teach in primary schools and there were also questions on understanding concerning attracting high achievers to teaching, including STEM in teacher preparation, professional development, and leadership in primary schools. The questionnaire included questions about intentions to teach STEM focused on the interest connected to daily life, the ability to apply mathematics, the need for primary teachers to be supported by a specialist STEM teacher, the needs for separate subject on STEM in the university for pre-service teachers' university programs, and the teachers' ability in STEM to transform creativity and innovation among children. Future teachers who answered the questionnaires placed emphasis on the fact that their knowledge of science and technology was minimal. However, they had positive intentions to teach STEM since they believed that STEM-related subjects are important for life.

Among the conclusions of the study are the following:

- Pre-service teachers should have experiences in STEM in order to apply their knowledge, their skills and the principles of STEM efficiently.
- Science knowledge and sound pedagogical practices should be integrated in order for teachers to practice STEM teaching in an optimal manner.
- Ongoing professional training in STEM education is necessary for all teachers.
- STEM should include school and non-school experiences in STEM-related activities (Kurup, Li, Powell & Brown, 2019).

Teachers' perception of knowledge, confidence, and efficacy for teaching STEM influences students' learning and classroom practices (Nadelson et al., 2013). Teachers' ability in integrating background knowledge of technological pedagogical content knowledge to a STEM curriculum seems a challenge to pre-service and in-service teachers (Hofer & Grandgenett, 2012). It is also essential for teachers to have a professional development education in STEM that would enable them to integrate disciplines and will provide them an understanding of teaching approaches that combine hands-on activities with the effort to develop twenty- first century competencies. Furthermore, there is a need

for policies of STEM that are based on the four-dimensional framework: knowledge, skills, character, meta-learning. (Bybee, 2013).

3. Playing with Protons program and its goals

In most countries, physics is taught in high-schools, in ways that don't motivate students and as a result they make them think that the subject is boring and useless for them. One of the reasons that in most cases science is taught only in high-schools is that there are not specialized science teachers in primary school and since modern physics can be a difficult subject, primary school teachers may lack the confidence and knowledge to perform well in the classroom (Wilkins, 2010). In this manner, they are excluded from the creative world of the modern scientific approaches that extend the boundaries of science in a way that physics can meet philosophy and imagination (Etkina, 2015).

However, according to several studies, the public wants science to be taught early in primary education. The majority of participants in the above-mentioned studies believe that science in primary school will help students to perform well in high-school. (Belden, Lien & Nelson-Dusek, 2010)

Eshach and Fried (Eshach& Fried, 2005) posited that even very young children should be exposed to the world of science. Their assertions are as follows: 1. Children normally find pleasure in observing and contemplating nature. 2. The exposure of young students to science results in the development and adoption of a positive attitude towards it. 3. Early exposure to scientific phenomena prompts to better comprehension of the scientific terms studied formally later. 4. The utilization of scientifically informed language at an early age affects the eventual development of scientific concepts in a very positive way. 5. Children can understand scientific concepts and reason scientifically. 6. Science is an efficient means for developing scientific thinking.

"Playing with Protons" was a CERN program addressed to primary school students. This idea that the concepts of modern physics and science in general should be taught at an early age represented the added value of the program. This course was initially supported by the CMS and subsequently by the ATLAS experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) within the framework of the CREATIONS EU project (CREATIONS EU project website) and after it was supported by the REINFORCE (REINFORCE EU project website) and FRONTIERS (FRONTIERS EU project website) European projects. In CREATIONS, 16 partners from 11 European countries developed creative approaches based on arts for an engaging science classroom in order to improve the skills of young people in STEM, raise student's interest and encourage science teachers to innovate. Combining science and art, partners were planning a variety of cultural events in which young people can experience an active and playful role within science and research. "Art@CMS", "Learning Science through Theater" and "Global Science Opera" were three of the programmes within the framework of the CREATIONS project. (CREATIONS EU project website).

The program focused on experiments conducted by the students themselves with everyday materials and objects and it resulted in the students becoming familiar with complicated scientific concepts as well as the latest developments in the field of particle physics research. Naturally, knowledge of modern physics should be explained to young students in a conceptual way rather than a mathematical way and a lot of hands-on activities should be utilized to provide a solid foundation to young students for a deeper understanding of scientific concepts (Alexopoulos&Nantsou, 2017).

The project was combined with training of primary teachers taking place at CERN (Trimoulla, 2016). Ten teachers from Greece and UK were selected in order to participate in the training program that took place at CERN's facilities. They experimented with simple materials and when they returned to their countries they diffused the knowledge they acquired to their colleagues and to their students. The main goals of the program were to enable primary school teachers to:

- Invent innovative scenarios and lesson plans to motivate their students and enrich the curriculum at the same time.

- Experience technology, science and innovation at CERN, which is the largest particle physics laboratory in the world.
- Get acquainted with new teaching approaches based on hands-on activities and experiments.
- Diffuse the knowledge they acquired at CERN to their colleagues, peers and local communities.
- Feel confident when teaching science.

"Playing with Protons" enabled primary teachers to improve their knowledge and teaching practices with creative methods that can attract the attention and get students engaged with science and technology ideas. The visit to CERN enabled teachers to transmit first-hand knowledge to students. Experiential learning for teachers ensures experiential learning for students. This is one of the most effective ways to attract the attention of students and to stimulate them. Furthermore, teachers became part of the scientific community and in this way they could transmit the values of collaboration towards common goals that furthered the progress of human civilization. All the above ensured that students would have a high-quality education experience when they participated in a CERN project.

"Playing with Protons" included continuing professional development (CPD) courses for primary school teachers, the development of learning resources and communities of interest, and continuous support for schools especially those in remote locations and schools with students who were members of relatively underprivileged communities. (CERN website).

The program allowed primary school teachers, specialists in science education and researchers working at CERN to cooperate in order to create new and original approaches that would increase the level of engagement in natural sciences, experimentation and innovation in primary school students. In particular, primary school teachers visited CERN experimental facilities to witness the one of a kind culture of the latest scientific discoveries, state-of-the-art technology and innovation at the largest particle physics laboratory on the planet. They drew inspiration and they became very eager to share the knowledge they have just discovered with peers, students, parents and the larger community. They experimented with new teaching activities focusing on hands-on activities using simple materials to increase their engagement level. Furthermore, they used innovative methods for the development of new educational scenarios and lesson plans that would make the teaching and learning process of physics more engaging and effective (Alexopoulos & Nantsou, 2017).

As a Flexible zone teacher in three Primary schools of Artemida, Athens, I had the opportunity to participate in the program "Playing with Protons". Considering that the main challenge of the program is to cultivate science, motivation and creativity in primary school students, throughout the program, students in nearly all primary school grades were involved in various creative activities. In particular, students performed artistic activities, constructions and general explorations of objects. They simulated physics experiments, they created collages and digital presentations for natural scientists. In addition, they depicted the CMS detector in multiple ways, using a variety of materials and techniques, including wood, collages, Lego, three-dimensional printing, and organizing an art exhibition at CMS, etc.

4. Selected lesson plan

4.1. Session 1 (powerpoint presentation & videos): Learn about CERN underground facilities. Engineering challenge: Create and build models and maquettes of CERN premises.

Session 2 (powerpoint presentation & videos): Learn about the CMS experiment and the science behind the experiment. Engineering challenge: Simulation of the CMS experiment.

Session 3 (powerpoint presentation & videos): The ATLAS and CMS detectors (learn the physics and engineering of the detectors). Engineering challenge: Construct models of a particle detector, like ATLAS and CMS) (with the use of everyday materials).

4.2. Scientific model

Phase 1: QUESTION: students investigate a scientifically oriented question

Balance and navigation through dialogue aid teachers and students in creatively navigating educational tensions. Ethics and trusteeship are an important consideration in experimental design and collaborative work, as well as in the initial choice of question.

Phase 2: EVIDENCE: students give priority to evidence

Risk, immersion and play are crucial in empowering pupils to generate, question and discuss.

Phase 3: ANALYSE: students analyze evidence

Students analyze evidence, using dialogue with each other and the teacher to support their developing understanding.

Phase 4: EXPLAIN: students formulate an explanation based on evidence

Students use evidence they have generated and analyzed to consider possibilities for explanations that are original to them. They use argumentation and dialogue.

Phase 5: CONNECT: students connect explanations to scientific knowledge

Students connect their explanations with scientific knowledge, using different ways of thinking and knowing ("knowing that", "knowing how", and "knowing this").

Phase 6: COMMUNICATE: students communicate and justify explanation

Communication of possibilities, ideas and justifications through dialogue with other students.

Phase 7: REFLECT: students reflect on the inquiry process and their learning

Individual, collaborative and community-based reflective activities consolidate learning and enable students and teachers.

4.3 Sessions

School: 4th Primary School of Artemida, Greece, Athens

Grades: 1st-6th grades of Primary education

SESSION 1

The Maquette of CERN's installations (construction, artistic representation)

Duration: 4 lessons X 45': 3h

Objectives

-Learn about CERN underground facilities.

-Engineering challenge: Create and build models and maquettes of CERN premises.

SESSION 2

Simulation of the CMS experiment with Led Flash Circuit and Led Chaser Circuit

Duration: 4 lessons x 45: 3h

Objectives

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- Learn about the CMS experiment and the science behind the experiment.
- Engineering challenge: Simulation of the CMS experiment.

SESSION 3

Models of a particle detector (CMS and ATLAS)

Duration: 13h30 approximately

Objectives

- The detectors CMS and ATLAS (learn the physics and engineering of the detectors)
- Construct models of a particle detector (CMS and ATLAS), [use of everyday materials].

SESSION 1 Themaquette of CERN's installations (constructions, artistic representations)

SESSION 2 [Simulation of the CMS experiment with Led Flash Circuit and Led Chaser Circuit](#)

SESSION 3 1. Miniatures of the CMS detector using Lego 2. Wooden representations of the CMS detector 3. a) Paintings about the CMS Detector and Art@CMS Exhibition b) art@CMS. A virtual Gallery-A collection of the best paintings at the art@CMS (CERN) of Michael Hoch, Lindsay Olson, Paco Falco, Chris Henschke, Xavier Cortada, Alison Gill made with the digital tool artsteps. c. The CMS detector was represented in collages (materials such as jewelry, drinking straws, pills, toothpicks, bottle caps and pasta were used). d. Collage of the particle detector CMS using the app Hp Reveal of the Augmented Reality on mobile and tablet. 4. 3D printing models of CERN (the process of printing and assembling the CMS detector lasted 100 hours. Additionally, 100 hours were required for printing the "Globe of science and innovation" and 2 hours for printing and assembling of little models of Higgs bosons). 5. The particle detector CMS dessert (a dessert consisting of butter, chocolate and sugar and weighing three kilograms). 6. "Playing with Particles", Applications for web and portable devices (cross-platform, Android - IOS) "Detecting particles" (CMS, CERN) (30minutes) Level 1&Level 2. It's a part of a complete course (26 applications) on particle physics using Flashcards and Games created with the Cram Web application. In particular, the theory is presented in six thematic units (13 applications) followed by exercises in the form of quizzes, created with the Quizglobal tool, that test and enhance the understanding of the theory (13 applications). 7. Models and Artistic representations of the particle detector ATLAS (CERN) with arts and crafts and using the technique "shadow and light". 8. Models of the Particle Detector CMS (CERN) created by the students made with the digital tool Powtoon. 9. Article on Wikipedia about the CMS experiment. 10. Poems about CERN set to music and visualized (inspired by astrophysics and particle physics). The Freinet technique was used for the creation of small books.

5. Challenges-Difficulties

The main challenge I had to face was related to the Greek curriculum which does not include modern physics. I had to redesign the syllabus and be innovative and creative. I used materials that motivated my students' creativity, such as Lego, clay, cardboards, etc. My teaching style is creative and innovative. This is the reason why I promoted STEAM literacy in primary students by encouraging them to become out-of-the-box thinkers and creators. Another challenge was that I should teach particle physics to very young children therefore I had to come up with activities suitable for their age and interests. New technologies, such as 3D printers, made a significant contribution. Children were very enthusiastic about science. A great outcome of the above-mentioned activities was the production of original audio-visual and digital material in the form of educational resources about physics and, in particular, particle physics, in collaboration with my students. I think this is a

valuable material for a wide range of people. In addition, the context in which I taught the program is a public primary school in an eastern suburb of Athens. The building and the infrastructure are in terrible condition, which made my efforts even more difficult. In addition, I had to deal with underprivileged children of low socio-economic and educational status.

6. Evaluation of the program

The follow-up evaluation showed that teachers experienced higher science teaching confidence, higher interest in physics and science in general and increased creativity. A great majority of teachers agreed that they implemented their knowledge and shared it with their peers. (Alexopoulos et al, 2018). The quantitative and qualitative data of tools including questionnaires and student interviews verified the positive acceptance of the program by both the students and the teachers who participated in it as well as by the parents. The contribution of the program to the connection of school knowledge with the needs, age, level and interests of students as well as real social situations was considered to be particularly valuable. Moreover, in this context, the creation of better relationships with all students and especially those with particular learning, cultural and linguistic needs was promoted. In addition, the "Playing with Protons" gave students the opportunity to develop general skills including collaboration, communication, creativity, problem-solving and presentation. Cross-curricular and creative activities broke cultural stereotypes associated with science and scientists and demonstrated the value of learning modern physics and science at an early age. In addition, teachers and students developed initiative actions, cultivated critical and creative thinking through methodologies related to a holistic and interdisciplinary approach to knowledge and the implementation of activities and projects at individual and group level which increased students' aspirations for science-related careers. The educational climate of the schools that implemented the program was positively influenced and this contributed to the promotion of creative cooperation between all involved in the educational process. Students were open and responsive to new and diverse perspectives, they demonstrated originality and inventiveness in work, higher order thinking and problem-solving skills and they elaborated original ideas to improve and maximize creative efforts.

Conclusions

The teaching implementations of the innovative "Playing with protons" program described above have provided students with a variety of opportunities to unravel their latent capabilities and broaden the perspectives through which they perceive the world and science. Designed teaching practices have mainly contributed to the students experimenting, identifying and discovering their strong and weak intelligences, inclinations and talents. At the same time, the use of appropriate digital tools has created the prerequisites for more efficient performance by students during the learning process, since the teaching work tailored to their individual profiles has led to the creative production of works along with the acquisition of self-regulating learning and autonomy skills as well as cooperation and communication. In conclusion, the implementation of the "Playing with Protons" program in primary education could be considered as contributing to the reforming of the teaching approach of various cognitive subjects, to the creation of a multipurpose, experiential learning environment, to the design of rich, polymorphic and multimodal courses and activities and to the selection of flexible techniques and strategies. Through the philosophy on which this innovative program was based, the students became more open towards science and society and the role of the teacher was upgraded, which is the most important factor for the success of any improvement in the education system.

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Effective teaching and learning methodologies in schools

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the various teaching and learning methodologies implemented in schools to enhance student learning outcomes. The methodologies discussed include Project-Based Learning, Flipped Classroom, Personalized Learning, Inquiry-Based Learning, Collaborative Learning, Technology-Enhanced Learning, Experiential Learning, Gamification, Differentiated Instruction, Formative Assessments, Social-Emotional Learning, Mastery Learning, Self-Directed Learning, and Problem-Based Learning. These methodologies aim to engage students, promote critical thinking, and develop essential skills for the 21st century. Effective implementation of these methodologies can lead to improved academic achievement, increased student motivation, and better preparation for future challenges.

These methodologies aim to:

- Enhance student engagement and motivation
- Develop critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills
- Foster a love for lifelong learning
- Prepare students for the 21st century workforce
- Support diverse learning needs and abilities
- Encourage active participation and ownership of learning
- Build strong teacher-student relationships

Keywords: Teaching Methodologies, Learning Strategies, Student-Centered Learning, Effective Instruction, School Education.

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the quest for effective teaching and learning methodologies remains paramount. As educators seek to engage diverse learners and meet the demands of a rapidly changing world, understanding and implementing innovative teaching strategies becomes imperative.

This article delves into the multifaceted realm of teaching and learning methodologies, exploring their significance, evolution, and impact on educational outcomes.

From traditional lecture-style instruction to interactive digital platforms, the spectrum of teaching methodologies is vast and continuously expanding. Each approach carries its unique strengths and challenges, influencing the dynamics of the classroom and shaping the learning experiences of students.

As educators navigate this rich tapestry of methodologies, they encounter a myriad of factors to consider, including learner preferences, curriculum objectives, and technological advancements.

Moreover, the efficacy of teaching methodologies transcends mere instructional techniques; it encompasses a holistic approach to education that fosters critical thinking, collaboration, and lifelong learning. By embracing innovative pedagogical practices, educators can cultivate dynamic learning environments where students are empowered to explore, create, and innovate.

This article seeks to unravel the complexities of teaching and learning methodologies, offering insights into their theoretical foundations, practical applications, and future directions.

Through an examination of research findings, case studies, and expert perspectives, readers will gain a comprehensive understanding of the diverse array of methodologies shaping contemporary education.

Teaching and Learning Methodologies refer to the approaches, strategies, and techniques used to facilitate student learning and achieve educational goals. Introducing effective Teaching and Learning Methodologies in schools can enhance the learning experience, improve student outcomes, and promote a supportive and inclusive learning environment.

METHODS

1. Literature Review:

- Conduct a comprehensive review of academic literature on teaching and learning methodologies. This involves gathering scholarly articles, books, and research papers from reputable sources.
- Identify key themes, trends, and debates within the field of educational pedagogy.
- Analyze the effectiveness of various teaching methodologies based on empirical evidence and theoretical frameworks.

2. Case Studies:

- Select relevant case studies that illustrate the implementation of different teaching methodologies in real-world educational settings.
- Gather data through interviews, observations, and document analysis to explore the impact of each methodology on student learning outcomes.
- Examine the contextual factors that influence the success or challenges of each teaching approach.

3. Surveys and Questionnaires:

- Design surveys or questionnaires to gather insights from educators, students, and other stakeholders regarding their experiences with different teaching methodologies.
- Include questions about preferred teaching styles, perceived effectiveness, and suggestions for improvement.
- Use quantitative analysis to identify trends and patterns in the data, as well as qualitative analysis to extract nuanced perspectives.

4. Interviews and Focus Groups:

- Conduct interviews with experienced educators, instructional designers, and educational researchers to gain expert insights into teaching and learning methodologies.
- Organize focus groups with diverse groups of students to explore their perceptions, preferences, and experiences with different instructional approaches.

- Utilize qualitative analysis techniques such as thematic coding to identify common themes and divergent viewpoints.
- 5. **Experimental Studies:**
 - Design experimental studies or quasi-experimental research to compare the effectiveness of different teaching methodologies.
 - Randomly assign participants to different instructional conditions and measure their learning outcomes using standardized assessments or performance tasks.
 - Control for extraneous variables and utilize statistical analysis to determine the relative impact of each teaching approach.
- 6. **Observational Research:**
 - Conduct observational research in classrooms to observe the implementation of various teaching methodologies in real-time.
 - Use structured observation protocols to systematically record teacher-student interactions, instructional strategies, and student engagement levels.
 - Analyze observational data to identify patterns of effective teaching practice and areas for improvement.

By employing a multi-method approach encompassing literature review, case studies, surveys, interviews, experimental studies, and observational research, this article aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of teaching and learning methodologies, their effectiveness, and implications for educational practice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. **Literature Review Findings:**
 - Summarize key findings from the literature review regarding the effectiveness of various teaching methodologies.
 - Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of each approach, as identified in the academic literature.
 - Explore the theoretical underpinnings and pedagogical principles that inform different teaching methodologies.
2. **Case Study Analysis:**
 - Present findings from the analysis of case studies, highlighting examples of successful implementation and challenges encountered.
 - Discuss how contextual factors, such as school culture, student demographics, and resource availability, influence the outcomes of different teaching methodologies.
 - Identify common themes and patterns across case studies, as well as unique insights gleaned from each example.
3. **Survey and Questionnaire Results:**
 - Summarize key findings from surveys and questionnaires regarding educator and student perceptions of teaching methodologies.
 - Discuss trends in preferred teaching styles, perceived effectiveness, and areas for improvement identified by survey respondents.
 - Compare and contrast the perspectives of educators and students on the utility of different instructional approaches.
4. **Interview and Focus Group Insights:**
 - Present insights gleaned from interviews with educators, instructional designers, and educational researchers.
 - Discuss expert opinions on the benefits, challenges, and future directions of teaching and learning methodologies.
 - Highlight common themes and divergent viewpoints expressed by interviewees, providing nuanced perspectives on effective pedagogy.
5. **Experimental Study Results:**
 - Present quantitative findings from experimental studies comparing the effectiveness of different teaching methodologies.

- Discuss statistically significant differences in student learning outcomes across instructional conditions.
 - Interpret the implications of experimental findings for educational practice and policy, considering factors such as instructional design, assessment methods, and student engagement.
6. **Observational Research Insights:**
- Summarize key insights from observational research conducted in classrooms.
 - Discuss observed patterns of effective teaching practice, including instructional strategies, classroom management techniques, and student interactions.
 - Reflect on the alignment between observed teaching behaviors and theoretical frameworks of effective pedagogy.
7. **Synthesis and Implications:**
- Synthesize the findings from various research methods to draw overarching conclusions about teaching and learning methodologies.
 - Discuss implications for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers seeking to improve educational practice.
 - Highlight areas for future research and innovation in the field of educational pedagogy, considering emerging technologies, cultural contexts, and evolving student needs.

By synthesizing findings from diverse research methods, this section aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of teaching and learning methodologies, offering insights into their effectiveness, challenges, and potential for enhancing student learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In the dynamic landscape of education, the quest for effective teaching and learning methodologies remains a perpetual journey, shaped by evolving pedagogical theories, technological innovations, and diverse student needs.

This article has undertaken a comprehensive exploration of the multifaceted realm of teaching and learning methodologies, drawing on a range of research methods to illuminate key insights and implications for educational practice.

Through a synthesis of literature review findings, case study analyses, survey data, interviews, experimental studies, and observational research, several overarching conclusions emerge:

1. **Diverse Pedagogical Landscape:** The field of education encompasses a rich tapestry of teaching methodologies, each with its unique strengths, challenges, and theoretical foundations. From traditional lecture-style instruction to experiential learning approaches, educators have a myriad of strategies at their disposal to engage learners and foster meaningful learning experiences.
2. **Contextual Considerations:** The effectiveness of teaching methodologies is intricately intertwined with contextual factors such as school culture, student demographics, and resource availability. What works in one educational setting may not necessarily yield the same outcomes in another, underscoring the importance of contextually responsive pedagogy.
3. **Student-Centered Learning:** A common thread across diverse teaching methodologies is the emphasis on student-centered learning, where learners are actively engaged in constructing knowledge, solving authentic problems, and collaborating with peers. By empowering students as co-creators of their learning experiences, educators can cultivate lifelong learners who are equipped to navigate an ever-changing world.
4. **Continuous Improvement:** Effective teaching and learning methodologies require a commitment to continuous improvement and reflective practice. Educators must critically evaluate their instructional approaches, solicit feedback from students and colleagues, and embrace opportunities for professional development to enhance their pedagogical repertoire.
5. **Future Directions:** As we look to the future of education, several emerging trends and opportunities warrant attention. From the integration of digital technologies to the promotion of global citizenship skills, educators must remain agile and adaptive in responding to the evolving needs of 21st-century learners.

In conclusion, the pursuit of effective teaching and learning methodologies is a multifaceted endeavor that requires collaboration, innovation, and a deep commitment to student success.

By embracing a diverse array of pedagogical approaches, informed by research, reflection, and evidence-based practice, educators can create dynamic learning environments where every student has the opportunity to thrive.

As we continue to navigate the complexities of education in the years ahead, let us remain steadfast in our dedication to excellence, equity, and the transformative power of education to shape a brighter future for all.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Promote Pedagogical Diversity:** Educational institutions should embrace a diverse range of teaching methodologies to cater to the diverse learning styles and preferences of students. By offering a variety of instructional approaches, educators can create inclusive learning environments that accommodate different learning needs and preferences.
2. **Invest in Professional Development:** Schools and districts should prioritize professional development opportunities for educators to enhance their pedagogical skills and stay abreast of emerging trends in teaching and learning. This may include workshops, seminars, peer mentoring programs, and online courses focused on effective instructional strategies and educational technologies.
3. **Foster Collaborative Learning Communities:** Educators should actively collaborate with colleagues, instructional coaches, and educational researchers to share best practices, troubleshoot challenges, and co-design innovative teaching approaches. By fostering a culture of collaboration and inquiry, schools can cultivate dynamic learning communities where continuous improvement is the norm.
4. **Integrate Technology Thoughtfully:** While technology can enhance teaching and learning experiences, its integration should be guided by pedagogical principles and educational goals. Schools should provide educators with training and support to effectively integrate digital tools and resources into their instructional practices, ensuring that technology enhances, rather than detracts from, student learning outcomes.
5. **Empower Student Voice and Choice:** Educators should actively involve students in the learning process by soliciting their feedback, providing opportunities for self-directed learning, and offering choice in how they demonstrate mastery of content. By empowering students as active participants in their education, educators can foster intrinsic motivation, autonomy, and a sense of ownership over their learning journey.
6. **Cultivate a Growth Mindset:** Schools should promote a growth mindset culture where failure is reframed as an opportunity for learning and improvement. Educators and students alike should be encouraged to embrace challenges, persist in the face of setbacks, and view mistakes as valuable learning experiences that contribute to growth and development.
7. **Advocate for Equity and Access:** Educational stakeholders should advocate for equitable access to high-quality teaching and learning resources for all students, regardless of their socioeconomic background, race, gender, or ability. This may involve addressing systemic barriers to educational equity, such as funding disparities, inequitable distribution of resources, and implicit bias in educational practices.

By implementing these recommendations, educational institutions can create learning environments that prioritize student engagement, foster deep learning, and empower learners to reach their full potential.

As we navigate the complexities of education in the 21st century, let us remain committed to advancing teaching and learning methodologies that promote equity, excellence, and lifelong learning for all.

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It is our collective commitment to empowering learners and fostering inclusive learning environments that motivates us to continue our work in the field of education.

In conclusion, we recognize that this article would not have been possible without the collaborative efforts of numerous individuals and organizations.

We are humbled by the opportunity to contribute to the ongoing dialogue surrounding teaching and learning methodologies and remain committed to advancing educational excellence for the betterment of society.

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ΔΗΜΙΟΥΡΓΙΑ ΔΥΝΑΜΗΣ ΑΠΟ ΤΗΝ ΤΑΧΥΤΗΤΑ

Εφαρμογή στις Μαχητικές Τέχνες

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Περίληψη

Στην παρούσα εργασία γίνεται μια απλή ανάλυση της παραγόμενης δύναμης όπως αυτή μπορεί να συσχετιστεί με τη μεταβολή της ταχύτητας και της ορμής και του χρόνου. Στην εκπαίδευση στις μαχητικές τέχνες η παραγωγή της δύναμης είναι πολύ σημαντική και έχει άμεση σχέση με την επίτευξη του αποτελέσματος και την δυναμική ισορροπία κατά την εκτέλεση μιας τεχνικής ή πιο περίπλοκους συνδυασμούς. Αναλύεται η σχέση της δύναμης με την ταχύτητα και την ορμή αλλά και του χρόνου δηλαδή τη διάρκεια της εφαρμογής που είναι πολύ σημαντικός παράγοντας και διερευνάται το αποτέλεσμα μέσω της κλασικής μηχανικής του Νεύτωνα. Επίσης η ανάλυση συσχετίζει την ικανότητα παραγωγής δύναμης ως προς το μυϊκό σύστημα σε σχέση οπωσδήποτε με την ελαστικότητα του μυϊκού συστήματος και την εκρηκτικότητα. Η έκρηξη και η ελαστικότητα του μυϊκού συστήματος είναι πολύ σημαντικές παράμετροι για την αρμονία και την πληρότητα στην τεχνική και την επίτευξη καλύτερης ισορροπίας, κινητικής ή στατικής από τον αθλητή κατά την εκτέλεση μιας τεχνικής που χρησιμοποιεί λεπτούς συνδυασμούς όπου συμμετέχει όλο το σώμα. Τα συμπεράσματα είναι σημαντικά και έχουν σχέση με την κλασική Φυσική και τη μελέτη των δυνάμεων, ενώ πρέπει να δίνεται ιδιαίτερη έμφαση στη λεπτότητα και την ακρίβεια των κινήσεων από τους εκπαιδευτές έτσι ώστε να χρησιμοποιούν τις διακεκριμένες ασκήσεις και τακτικές εκμάθησης των συνδυασμών και οι αθλητές να μπορούν κατά το βέλτιστο τρόπο να επιτυγχάνουν το καλύτερο δυνατό αποτέλεσμα για την παραγωγή της δύναμης παράλληλα με την επίτευξη ισορροπίας με την σύγχρονη την επίτευξη της εκρηκτικότητας.

Λέξεις Κλειδιά: Δύναμη, ορμή, Ταχύτητα, Χρόνος, Μυϊκή Ελαστικότητα

Εισαγωγή

Η δύναμη είναι ένα μέγεθος που μπορεί να επιφέρει πολλές και διακριτές αλλαγές στην κίνηση και σχετίζεται με το αποτέλεσμα που θα μπορεί να παράγει. Μεγέθη που σχετίζονται με τη δύναμη και τη μεταβολή που μπορεί να παράγει είναι η ορμή ενός σώματος, η μεταβολή στην ταχύτητα, η μεταβολή στην ενέργεια του σώματος και η παραγωγή ή σπατάλη έργου.

Ιδιαίτερα στον τομέα της άθλησης και της κίνησης του ανθρωπίνου σώματος η δύναμη παίζει ουσιαστικό ρόλο. Πολύ σημαντική είναι ιδιαίτερα στον τομέα εφαρμογών των μαχητικών αθλημάτων.

Πολλές φορές κατά την προπόνηση ή σε μια πραγματική εφαρμογή, προσπαθούμε να επιτύχουμε μεγάλη δύναμη και συνεπώς μεγάλη ισχύ. Αυτό μπορεί να συμβαίνει στην περίπτωση ενός κτυπήματος είτε σε λάκτισμα, είτε σε κάποια εφαρμοζόμενη τεχνική ή χτύπημα με τα χέρια, επί παραδείγματι μια γροθιά.

Τις περισσότερες φορές δίνουμε μικρή σημασία σε μεγέθη που πραγματικά έχουν άμεση σχέση με την κίνησή μας. Αυτό μπορεί πιθανόν να οφείλεται στη έλλειψη γνώσεων που μπορεί να σχετίζονται ειδικότερα με την Εργοφυσιολογία και τη Φυσική ή τη Βιοκινητική. Αν και τα

φαινόμενα στην καθημερινότητα είναι μάλλον πιο απλά και αυτό θα αναλυθεί στο άρθρο αυτό για να γίνει κατανοητή η μεταβολή ορισμένων μεγεθών που σχετίζονται με την κίνηση και μπορούν να έχουν άμεση σχέση με την παραγωγή δύναμης. (Drougas V. (2018)).

Η Δύναμη σαν Φυσικό Μέγεθος

Η δύναμη είναι ένα μέγεθος της φυσικής μετρήσιμο με ειδικά όργανα που ονομάζονται δυναμόμετρα και έχουν την δυνατότητα να μας δίνουν με ακρίβεια την τιμή της. Μπορεί να εφαρμόζεται από ένα σώμα στο άλλο και να παράγει μεταβολές στην κινητική κατάσταση αλλά και την ισορροπία ενός σώματος. Δύο ή περισσότερες δυνάμεις που εξασκούνται προς την ίδια κατεύθυνση μπορούν να παράγουν μια συνισταμένη δύναμη που βρίσκεται από το

άθροισμα κάθε μιας από τις εφαρμοζόμενες δυνάμεις. Έτσι όλες μαζί μπορούν να παράγουν πολύ μεγαλύτερο αποτέλεσμα από ότι θα δημιουργούσε κάθε μία χωριστά αν εφαρμοζόταν στο ίδιο σώμα. Αν σε ένα σώμα εφαρμόζονται για παράδειγμα δύο αντίθετες δυνάμεις τότε το σώμα συμπεριφέρεται σαν να δέχεται μια συνισταμένη δύναμη που έχει μέτρο δηλαδή τιμή όσο η διαφορά των δύο δυνάμεων.

Είναι πολύ σημαντικό να αντιληφθούμε ότι η δύναμη δεν παράγεται μόνο από τους μύες, αλλά είναι το αποτέλεσμα μιας συνεργασίας πολλών διαφορετικών μεγεθών και μελών του σώματός μας και φυσικά της μυϊκής μας ελαστικότητας. (Drougas V. (2008)).

Σχετίζεται με την στροφή του σώματος, την ώθηση που δίνει ο κορμός κατά την κίνηση, τη σωστή στάση, την κινητική ισορροπία, την ταλάντωση που μπορεί να κάνει ο κορμός κατά την κίνηση και τη δύναμη αντίδρασης από το έδαφος κυρίως αυτή, η οποία προκύπτει από το πέλμα συνήθως του ποδιού που έπεται της κατεύθυνσης της κίνησης, που αποδίδει την ώθηση προς τα μπρός.

Όμως η δύναμη από τη φυσική σχετίζεται με ένα μέγεθος που μπορεί από την κλασική μηχανική να έχει άμεση σχέση με την παραγωγή της και την αριθμητική της ποσότητα κατά την κίνηση.

Το μέγεθος αυτό με το οποίο σχετίζεται η δύναμη είναι η ορμή. Αυτή αντιπροσωπεύει το γινόμενο της ταχύτητας πολλαπλασιασμένο επί την μάζα του κινούμενου σώματος, εν προκειμένω του μέλους του σώματός μας που χρησιμοποιούμε σε κάποια εφαρμογή.

Έτσι λοιπόν μια μεγαλύτερη μάζα παράγει μεγαλύτερη ορμή και φυσικά η μεγαλύτερη ταχύτητα επίσης την πολλαπλασιάζει. Ο μαθηματικός τύπος που περιγράφει το μέγεθος της ορμής στη Φυσική είναι $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{m}\cdot\mathbf{U}$ όπου m είναι η μάζα του κινούμενου σώματος και $\mathbf{U}$ είναι η ταχύτητά του. Η μεταβολή τώρα της ορμής όταν μεταβάλλεται η ταχύτητα δίνεται από τον τύπο $\Delta\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{m}\cdot\Delta\mathbf{U}$ όπου το $\Delta\mathbf{U}$ παριστάνει τη μεταβολή της ταχύτητας.

Θα σας δώσω ένα παράδειγμα για να καταλάβετε πιο εύκολα αυτή τη μεταβολή.

Αν θεωρήσουμε ότι η γροθιά μας κινείται με **40** μέτρα ανά δευτερόλεπτο τότε τη στιγμή που θα κτυπήσει πάνω σε ένα εμπόδιο θα μηδενιστεί ακαριαία η ταχύτητά της εφόσον δεν θα επιτρέπεται να διαπεράσει το εμπόδιο και εφόσον αυτό δεν έχει ελαστικότητα.

Έτσι λοιπόν η μεταβολή θα πάρει την τιμή $\Delta U = 40 \text{ m/sec}$, μετρήσιμη σε μέτρα το δευτερόλεπτο, όσο δηλαδή η αρχική τιμή της πριν να χτυπήσει στο στόχο.

Αν δούμε τον τύπο που περιγράφει τη σχέση της δύναμης με τη μεταβολή της ορμής, σύμφωνα με τη Νευτώνεια Μηχανική, για ένα σώμα από τη Φυσική θα έχουμε τον τύπο υπολογισμού: $F = \Delta P / \Delta t$. Όπου ΔP είναι η Αριθμητική μεταβολή της Ορμής τους σώματος και Δt το χρονικό διάστημα που απαιτήθηκε για τη μεταβολή της ταχύτητας άρα και της ορμής.

Αυτός ο τύπος δείχνει ότι η δύναμη που αντιστοιχεί στη μεταβολή της ορμής κατά την κίνηση ενός σώματος σχετίζεται και με το χρονικό διάστημα αυτής της μεταβολής.

Δηλαδή με το πόσο γρήγορα αλλάζει η κίνησή μας στο χρόνο.

Μάλιστα όσο πιο μικρό είναι το χρονικό διάστημα αυτό που θα μεσολαβήσει, τόσο μεγαλύτερη είναι και η δύναμη που ισοδυναμεί σε αυτή τη μεταβολή.

Αυτό φυσικά δεν συμβαίνει μόνο όταν το σώμα που μελετάμε σταματάει δηλαδή παύει να έχει ταχύτητα αλλά και σε οποιαδήποτε άλλη περίπτωση ακόμα και όταν αλλάζει η κατεύθυνση της κίνησης που κάνουμε. Για παράδειγμα σε μια περίπτωση που χρησιμοποιούμε το σώμα μας για αποφυγή ή για μια παράκαμψη ή μια παραπλανητική κίνηση.

Έτσι μπορούμε να παράγουμε μεγάλη δύναμη F σε κάθε περίπτωση λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τους δύο επόμενους τρόπους.

1ος τρόπος να κινηθούμε πολύ γρήγορα δηλαδή να αποκτήσουμε μεγαλύτερη ταχύτητα και

2ος τρόπος να επιτύχουμε μεταβολή πολύ σύντομα δηλαδή σε μικρό χρονικό διάστημα.

Φυσικά αν συσχετίσουμε και τα δύο, δηλαδή αύξηση της ταχύτητας και ελάττωση του χρόνου στο χτύπημα ή στη μεταβολή της τότε η δύναμη που θα παραχθεί θα είναι πολύ πιο μεγάλη. Θέλω να επισημάνω ότι τα ίδια συμβαίνουν και στην περίπτωση που η ταχύτητα τείνει να ελαττωθεί απλά η δύναμη έχει πλέον διαφορετική κατεύθυνση.

Σκεφθείτε τον παρακάτω συλλογισμό. Για να σταματήσω ένα αυτοκίνητο που έχει αναπτύξει κάποια ταχύτητα θα πρέπει να εφαρμόσω σε αυτό μια αντίθετη δύναμη από την κίνηση του δηλαδή από εκείνη την κατεύθυνση που είχε το σώμα όταν κινούνταν.

Κάτι ανάλογο συμβαίνει και με τα φρένα του αυτοκινήτου για να σταματήσει.

Αν όμως θέλουμε το ίδιο αυτοκίνητο να αποκτήσει μεγαλύτερη ταχύτητα θα πρέπει να εφαρμόσουμε σε αυτό μια δύναμη που θα έχει την ίδια κατεύθυνση με την κίνηση του οχήματος. Αυτό μεταφράζεται στη Φυσική σαν δύναμη που προκύπτει από τη μεταβολή της ταχύτητας.

Σκεφθείτε τη δύναμη που δέχεται ένα αυτοκίνητο όταν χτυπάει πάνω σε ένα εμπόδιο και σταματάει.

Στην περίπτωση της μετωπικής κρούσης αυτή είναι υπερβολικά μεγάλη και έχει κατεύθυνση από το εμπόδιο προς το όχημα. Το αντίθετο όμως θα συμβεί στην περίπτωση που το όχημα δεχθεί ένα χτύπημα από πίσω καθώς μετακινείται με αποτέλεσμα να αυξηθεί η ταχύτητά του. Τότε η δύναμη θα έχει την ίδια κατεύθυνση με την κατεύθυνση της κίνησης του οχήματος και φυσικά θα το επιταχύνει.

Αυτό για παράδειγμα έχει σημαντική εφαρμογή στην περίπτωση που ωθούμε κάποιον προς μια ρίψη ή εξοστρακίζουμε την τεχνική του όπως συμβαίνει στην περίπτωση των τεχνικών αποφυγής και αλλαγής δράσης κατεύθυνσης.

Το παρακάτω σχήμα δείχνει πως μπορούμε με τη δύναμη να αυξήσουμε την ταχύτητα και το αντίστροφο, δηλαδή η αύξηση της ταχύτητας να έχει προκύψει από κάποια σχετική δύναμη πάνω στο σώμα.

Στο **Σχήμα 1** Η δύναμη που επιδράει στο σώμα έχει την ίδια φορά με την ταχύτητα και η εφαρμογή της στο σώμα αυξάνει στην ταχύτητα του σώματος

Σχήμα 1

Επίδραση δύναμης σε σώμα με φορά ίδια με την φορά της ταχύτητας

Η κίνησή όμως αλλάζει με ελάττωση της ταχύτητας του σώματος όταν η δύναμη έχει αντίθετη φορά από την κίνηση **Σχήμα 2**

Σχήμα 2

Επίδραση δύναμης σε σώμα με φορά αντίθετη με την φορά της ταχύτητας

Στις δύο παραπάνω περιπτώσεις η αλλαγή στην κατεύθυνση της δύναμης επιδράει ανάλογα και στην ταχύτητα.

Έχω θεωρήσει για λόγους απλότητας και κατανόησης την κίνηση πάνω σε μια ευθύγραμμη τροχιά.

Ας δούμε όμως για τον παραπάνω συλλογισμό ένα απλό αριθμητικό παράδειγμα.

Αν θεωρήσουμε ότι η γροθιά μας κατευθύνεται σε ένα στόχο με την ταχύτητα των **40m/sec** (μέτρων ανά δευτερόλεπτο), τότε αν μπορέσουμε να έχουμε επαφή με το στόχο τη στιγμή του μηδενισμού της παραπάνω ταχύτητας μέσα σε **1 sec** (δευτερόλεπτο), τότε η δύναμη που θα παράγουμε αντιστοιχεί σε **40:1=40** Νιούτον.

Αν όμως η διάρκεια της κρούσης της γροθιάς στο στόχο γίνει μόλις **0,5 sec** δευτερόλεπτα τότε η δύναμη που θα παραχθεί κατά την επαφή θα είναι για την ίδια ταχύτητα **40:0,5=80** Νιούτον. Παρατηρούμε λοιπόν ότι η δύναμη πολλαπλασιάζεται αντίστροφα ανάλογα με το χρόνο και αυτό είναι πολύ σημαντικό στις παρατηρήσεις μας και στην παραγωγή δύναμης.

Αν κάποιος λοιπόν αθλητής δεν μπορεί να επιτύχει πολύ μεγάλες ταχύτητες αλλά μπορεί να εκπαιδευτεί να διατηρεί την επαφή στο χτύπημα πολύ μικρό χρόνο θα παράγει εξίσου πολύ μεγάλη δύναμη σε μικρό χρόνο.

Ας δούμε ένα απλό μαθηματικό διάγραμμα για να καταλάβουμε τι πραγματικά συμβαίνει.

Από το διάγραμμα που ακολουθεί μπορούμε να παρατηρήσουμε ότι όσο μεγαλώνει ο χρόνος που αντιστοιχεί στη διάρκεια της επαφής τόσο η δύναμη μικραίνει και μάλιστα αυτή η ελάττωση συμβαίνει πολύ απότομα. Τα ίδια ισχύουν ακόμα και όταν η δύναμη επιδράει εν κινήσει.

Αντίθετα όταν ο χρόνος μικραίνει τότε η δύναμη αυξάνεται πολύ απότομα.

Πρέπει λοιπόν να δοθεί σημαντικό βάρος στην εκπαίδευση ώστε να μπορεί κάποιος να επιτύχει πολύ μεγάλες ταχύτητες κατά την εφαρμογή μιας τεχνικής και μάλιστα να επιτυγχάνει πολύ μικρό χρόνο κρούσης.

Μπορείτε να ανατρέξετε σε προηγούμενο άρθρο μου, που σχετίζεται με τη μυϊκή ελαστικότητα για την παραγωγή μεγάλης ταχύτητας κατά την κίνηση ενός μέλους του σώματός μας για να κατανοήσετε την αξία της μυϊκής ελαστικότητας.

Στο άρθρο μου αυτό περιγράφω ότι η μυϊκή ελαστικότητα παίζει πολύ σημαντικό ρόλο στην ανάπτυξη ταχύτητας.

Για να επιτύχουμε όμως πολύ μικρό χρόνο κατά την επαφή θα πρέπει να δουλέψουμε πάρα πολύ την ικανότητα των μυών μας να παρέχουν ανακλαστικές ικανότητες και να παράγουν γρήγορα και ελαστικά δυνάμεις επαναφοράς μια διαδικασία που μπορεί να επιτευχθεί πιο αποτελεσματικά μέσω κυκλικών κινήσεων γύρω από τον κορμό. (Drougas V. (2024)).

Ένας σκληρός και ογκώδης μυς δεν μπορεί να το καταφέρει αυτό πολύ εύκολα, ούτε και μια μυϊκή ομάδα που έχει εκπαιδευτεί να παράγει δύναμη μόνο κατά ένα τρόπο χωρίς να συνεργάζεται αποτελεσματικά και με σχετικές με αυτήν μυϊκές ομάδες μικρότερες μεν αλλά ουσιαστικής σημασίας δεν μπορεί να αποδώσει το μέγιστο στην ισχύ.

Η μέγιστη ισχύς αποδίδεται με τη χρήση του κύκλου στην κίνηση. (Drougas V. (2022))

Πρέπει επίσης να λάβουμε υπόψη ότι με την αύξηση της ηλικίας μας, οι μύες χάνουν την ελαστικότητά τους και γίνονται λιγότερο παραγωγικοί ενώ αν δεν έχουμε φροντίσει να τους κάνουμε να συνεργάζονται μεταξύ τους και μάλιστα και με τις μικρότερες μυϊκές ομάδες αυτό το αποτέλεσμα που θα βλέπουμε με την πάροδο των χρόνων θα είναι πραγματικά απογοητευτικό.

Έτσι η εκπαίδευση με βάρη σηκώνοντας μεγάλες ποσότητες κιλών λιγότερο ωφελεί από ότι θα μπορούσαμε να καταφέρουμε αν χρησιμοποιούσαμε βάρη πολύ μικρότερων κιλών και μάλιστα κάνοντας εκρηκτικές επαναλήψεις.

Αν και η άποψη των επιστημόνων συμπίπτει εδώ με την άποψη των παραδοσιακών Μάστερ που τονίζουν ότι η εκπαίδευση στη σκιαμαχία δηλαδή σε εικονικό στόχο κάνει όλες τις μυϊκές ομάδες να αποκτούν μεγαλύτερη ελαστικότητα και συνεκτικότητα μεταξύ τους κατά τη χρήση τους.

Η εικονική μάχη και η προσπάθεια για επίτευξη υψηλών ταχυτήτων βοηθάει στην παραγωγή εκρηκτικών κινήσεων και μοντέλων μυϊκής συνεκτικότητας, τα οποία συνεργατικά μπορούν να προσφέρουν πολύ μεγαλύτερη ισχύ από ότι αν θα χρησιμοποιούνταν τυποποιημένα μόνο μια μυϊκή ομάδα και με έναν δεδομένο τρόπο χρήσης της (Drougas V. (2021)).

Πρέπει να γνωρίζουμε ότι κάθε χρονική στιγμή το μοντέλο της μάχης αλλάζει και έτσι και η ικανότητα χρήσης μιας μόνο διακεκριμένης τεχνικής πέφτει στο κενό, αυτός είναι και ο πιο σημαντικός ίσως λόγος, που τις περισσότερες φορές σε ελεύθερη μάχη είναι λιγιστές εκείνες

οι τεχνικές, που αποδίδουν το μέγιστο της δύναμης που προσπαθούμε να επιτύχουμε ή τουλάχιστον που θα περιμέναμε.

Τι θα πρέπει τελικά να κάνουμε σε μια προπόνηση, που θέλουμε να επιτύχουμε το μέγιστο δυνατό και καλύτερο αποτέλεσμα από πλευράς ισχύος και φυσικά ισορροπίας.

Προτάσεις για την κίνηση

Όταν θέλουμε να επιτύχουμε κινητική και στατική ισορροπία, τότε όλες οι μυϊκές ομάδες θα πρέπει να εκπαιδευτούν ώστε να συνεργάζονται τέλεια μεταξύ τους όποτε αυτή η συνεργασία απαιτηθεί. Αυτό απαιτεί χρόνια και διαρκή εκπαίδευση και προσαρμογή στον στόχο και την τακτική

Που θα πρέπει να στοχεύουμε;

- Να αποκτήσουμε μυϊκή ελαστικότητα.
- Να μπορούμε να παράγουμε μεγάλη ταχύτητα κατά την κίνηση, ας το ονομάσουμε αυτό εκρηκτικότητα. Έχει σχέση με τη μυϊκή ελαστικότητα. Αυτό θα γίνει και με την συνεργασία του κορμού με ελαστικές στροφές σε μικρό χρόνο.
- Να περιορίσουμε την σκληρότητα των μυών της πλάτης και των ραχιαίων μυών περιορίζοντας και τις δυναμικές ασκήσεις που αναφέρονται στους μύες της περιοχής αυτής.
- Να αποκτήσουμε ελαστικότητα των μυών της λεκάνης που έχουν σχέση με την στροφική κίνηση και τη διατήρηση της ελαστικότητας στα εκρηκτικά λακτίσματα.
- Να αποκτήσουμε δυναμικά, σωστή και ευέλικτη στάση που θα μπορεί να αλλάζει πολύ εύκολα (αυτό σχετίζεται με ένα γεωμετρικά και δυναμικά σωστό πάτημα στο έδαφος που ελαφρύνει τις δυνάμεις δράσης και μεταβάλλει τις συνιστώσες δυνάμεις στις αρθρώσεις λεκάνης γονάτου και ταρσού).
- Να επιτύχουμε μέγιστα αντανεκλαστικά και μικρό χρόνο επαφής της κρούσης με το στόχο.
- Οι Πολλές επαναλήψεις στην τεχνική που θα εφαρμόσουμε παίζει ουσιαστικό ρόλο στον συγχρονισμό των τεχνικών και τη συμμετοχή των μυϊκών ομάδων στην εφαρμόσιμη τεχνική.
- Νοητική Συγκέντρωση και συσχέτιση με το στόχο.
- Βελτίωση της συνολικής ελαστικότητας του κορμού, που θα μας βοηθήσει στην επίτευξη καλής συνεργασίας μεταξύ διαφορετικών μυϊκών ομάδων και στην αλτική μας ικανότητα.

Είναι σημαντικό σε κάθε περίπτωση επίσης να γνωρίζουμε ότι ένα ουσιαστικά μετρήσιμο αποτέλεσμα δεν επέρχεται ποτέ γρήγορα απαιτείται κόπος, επανάληψη, διάρκεια, επιμονή στο στόχο, βελτίωση σφαιρικά της σωματικής μας και της φυσικής μας κατάστασης και τέλος μια διαρκή πνευματική και σωματική χαλάρωση. Αυτό σχετίζεται άμεσα με τον τρόπο ζωής την διαρκή άσκηση και τη διατροφή αλλά και την μείωση του στρες (Drougas V. (2018)).

Πρέπει να γίνει κατανοητό ότι όσο περισσότερη δύναμη βάζουμε στην κίνηση τόσο οι μύες μας, γίνονται λιγότερο αποδοτικοί κατά την επαφή και φυσικά ο χρόνος που μετρήσαμε

παραπάνω μεγαλώνει με αποτέλεσμα η δύναμη που παράγεται κατά την επαφή να γίνεται κατά πολύ μικρότερη.

Συμπεράσματα

Η παραγωγή της δύναμης παίζει ουσιαστικό ρόλο στην κίνηση και της εφαρμογής μιας διακεκριμένης τεχνικής στις μαχητικές τέχνες. Είναι πολύ σημαντικό να αντιληφθούμε τις φυσικές μεταβλητές που σχετίζονται με την κίνηση οι οποίες είναι διαφορετικές για κάθε άνθρωπο και κάθε ηλικία.

Πρέπει να δοθεί ιδιαίτερο βάρος στην εκπαιδευτική διαδικασία στην επίτευξη συντεταγμένων παραμέτρων με την ταχύτητα και τη δύναμη για τη επίτευξη του καλύτερου δυνατού αποτελέσματος σε βάθος χρόνου. Κρίνεται σημαντική επίσης η διαρκής ενημέρωση και επιμόρφωση από ειδικούς επιστήμονες ώστε να επιτευχθεί το μέγιστο δυνατό αποτέλεσμα στην εκπαίδευση.

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Διδακτικό σενάριο : Δημιουργία σχολικής εφημερίδας

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ABSTRACT

The presence of foreign language students in the modern multilingual and multicultural school demands their equal participation in the learning process through cooperative and differentiated teaching. This teaching intervention is addressed to heterogeneous classes of primary schools. It is based on the new curricula for the Modern Greek Language and is thematically oriented towards the creation of a school newspaper.

The intervention is an indicative scenario that utilizes a) the communicative approach, b) teaching based on language processing, c) learning strategies and d) student-focused error analysis and correction, in order to be introduced in information situations, through communication. Assessment is a dynamic and cumulative process: their progress is evident from the improvement of their communication skills in the classroom but also inside and outside the school. The final product of the teaching scenario is the creation of a school newspaper, in order to involve the children in real communication situations and to practically evaluate the achievement of the goals set.

Keywords: Language, article writing, written language, school newspaper

ΠΕΡΙΛΗΨΗ

Η παρουσία αλλόγλωσσων μαθητών και μαθητριών στο σύγχρονο πολύγλωσσο και πολυπολιτισμικό σχολείο αξιώνει την ισότιμη συμμετοχή τους στη μαθησιακή διαδικασία μέσω ομαδοσυνεργατικής αλλά και διαφοροποιημένης διδασκαλίας. Η παρούσα διδακτική παρέμβαση απευθύνεται σε ανομοιογενείς τάξεις των δημοτικών σχολείων. Βασίζεται στα νέα προγράμματα σπουδών για τη Νεοελληνική Γλώσσα και είναι θεματικά προσανατολισμένη στη δημιουργία σχολικής εφημερίδας. Η παρέμβαση αποτελεί ένα ενδεικτικό σενάριο που αξιοποιεί α) την επικοινωνιακή προσέγγιση, β) τη διδασκαλία βάσει γλωσσικής επεξεργασίας, γ) τις στρατηγικές μάθησης και δ) την εστιασμένη στον/ στην μαθητή/τρια ανάλυση και διόρθωση λαθών, προκειμένου να εισαχθεί σε περιστάσεις ενημέρωσης, μέσω της επικοινωνίας. Η αξιολόγηση είναι μια δυναμική και αθροιστική διαδικασία: η πρόοδός τους διαφαίνεται από τη βελτίωση της επικοινωνιακής τους ικανότητας μέσα στη σχολική

τάξη αλλά και μέσα και έξω από το σχολείο. Το τελικό προϊόν του διδακτικού σεναρίου είναι η δημιουργία σχολικής εφημερίδας, προκειμένου να εμπλακούν τα παιδιά σε πραγματικές περιστάσεις επικοινωνίας και να αξιολογηθεί έμπρακτα η επίτευξη των στόχων που τέθηκαν.

Λέξεις-κλειδιά: Γλώσσα, αρθρογραφία, γραπτός λόγος, σχολική εφημερίδα.

1. Εισαγωγή

Στον σημερινό γρήγορα εξελισσόμενο κόσμο, οι συνεργατικές δραστηριότητες στην τάξη έχουν γίνει πιο σημαντικές από ποτέ. Η συνεργασία με τους συμμαθητές όχι μόνο ενισχύει τις εκπαιδευτικές εμπειρίες των μαθητών αλλά τους προετοιμάζει και για καταστάσεις στις οποίες η ομαδική εργασία είναι ουσιώδης. Ένας δυναμικός και διαδραστικός τρόπος για τους μαθητές να εφαρμόσουν τις δεξιότητές τους στον τομέα της γραφής, της επεξεργασίας, της σχεδίασης και της ομαδικής εργασίας είναι η δημιουργία μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας. Οι συνεργατικές δραστηριότητες, όπως το έργο της σχολικής εφημερίδας, παρέχουν στους μαθητές μια πλατφόρμα για να εκφράσουν τις ιδέες τους, να εκφράσουν τις απόψεις τους και να αλληλεπιδράσουν με τη σχολική κοινότητα. Μέσω της συνεργασίας για την επίτευξη ενός κοινού στόχου, οι μαθητές αναπτύσσουν και κρίσιμες δεξιότητες του 21ου αιώνα, όπως η επικοινωνία, η κριτική σκέψη και η επίλυση προβλημάτων. Αυτό το άρθρο αποτελεί μια διδακτική πρόταση για μαθητές και μαθήτριες της Στ' τάξης, για τη δημιουργία μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας στα πλαίσια της ικανότητάς τους να παράγουν σύντομα ή αναλυτικά εξηγητικά κείμενα που σχετίζονται με τις κοινωνικές πραγματικότητες που βιώνουν.

2. Το Νέο Πρόγραμμα Σπουδών Νεοελληνικής Γλώσσας στο Δημοτικό

Σύμφωνα με τη σκοποθεσία του ΝΠΣ για τη Νεοελληνική Γλώσσα στο Δημοτικό (ΝΠΣ, 2022), το μάθημα της Γλώσσας θεωρείται διαχρονικά ως το βασικότερο γνωστικό αντικείμενο της Πρωτοβάθμιας Εκπαίδευσης από την πλειονότητα των εκπαιδευτικών συστημάτων. Ο θεμελιακός ρόλος της Γλώσσας στη βαθμίδα αυτή πηγάζει από τη διττή φύση της, ως ατομικού γνωρίσματος και ως κοινωνικού αγαθού. Ως ατομικό γνώρισμα, η γλωσσική ικανότητα επιτρέπει στον/στη μαθητή/-τρια την πρόσληψη και παραγωγή γλωσσικών ερεθισμάτων, την επίτευξη της διαπροσωπικής επικοινωνίας, τη συγκρότηση της σκέψης και την απόκτηση γνώσεων. Σε κοινωνικό επίπεδο, οι μαθητές/-τριες, ως μέλη μιας κοινότητας, επιτυγχάνουν, μέσω των γλωσσικών πράξεων, την οικειοποίηση μιας σειράς αντίστοιχων πολιτισμικών στοιχείων, την αξιοποίηση προγενέστερων γνώσεων και εμπειριών, τη συνεργασία και την αλληλεπίδραση με τους εκάστοτε συμμετέχοντες για τον προσδιορισμό και την επίτευξη των κοινών τους στόχων.

Με δεδομένη την κατάκτηση της γλώσσας από το παιδί πριν τη σχολική ηλικία, η διδασκαλία της μητρικής (πρώτης) γλώσσας σε φυσικούς/-ές ομιλητές/-τριες επικεντρώνεται στην εκμάθηση του γραπτού λόγου (γραφή και ανάγνωση), στον ευρύτερο γραμματισμό των μαθητών/-τριών σε ποικιλία μέσων και περικειμένων, στην καλλιέργεια της προφορικής έκφρασης σε πλήθος επικοινωνιακών πλαισίων, στη βαθύτερη συνειδητοποίηση των λειτουργιών και της σημασίας της πρότυπης ποικιλίας και των άλλων ποικιλιών και στην ανάπτυξη της γλωσσικής επίγνωσης. Ανώτερος στόχος της γλωσσικής διδασκαλίας είναι όλοι/-ες οι μαθητές/-τριες να διευρύνουν το πεδίο της σκέψης τους και να είναι σε θέση να εκφράζονται στον προφορικό και γραπτό λόγο με ευχέρεια, ακρίβεια και πραγματολογική καταλληλότητα, ώστε να μεταδίδουν τις ιδέες και τις αξιολογήσεις τους στο περιβάλλον τους και να επικοινωνούν ενεργά μέσω της παραγωγής και της πρόσληψης του λόγου (ΝΠΣ, 2022).

Το πρόγραμμα σπουδών της διδασκαλίας της Νεοελληνικής Γλώσσας επικεντρώνεται στην ανάπτυξη δεξιοτήτων ακρόασης, ομιλίας, ανάγνωσης και γραφής. Οι διδακτικές προσεγγίσεις είναι ποικίλες και περιλαμβάνουν μεθόδους όπως η επικοινωνιακή γλωσσοδιδασκτική, η μέθοδος του ολικού φυσικού ανταποκριτικού, και η διαθεματική προσέγγιση (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). Οι

στόχοι περιλαμβάνουν την ενίσχυση της ικανότητας των μαθητών να επικοινωνούν αποτελεσματικά σε καθημερινές και ακαδημαϊκές καταστάσεις, την εξοικείωση με την ελληνική κουλτούρα, και την ανάπτυξη κριτικής σκέψης μέσω της γλώσσας (Byram, 1997).

3. Η Δημιουργία Σχολικής Εφημερίδας

Η δημιουργία μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας είναι μια διδακτική πρόταση που ενσωματώνει πολλές από τις δεξιότητες και τους στόχους του νέου προγράμματος σπουδών της Νεοελληνικής Γλώσσας στο Δημοτικό. Προάγοντας την ομαδική εργασία και τη συνεργασία, οι μαθητές αναλαμβάνουν διαφορετικούς ρόλους όπως συντάκτες, δημοσιογράφοι, φωτογράφοι, και γραφίστες (Johnson & Johnson, 1999). Επιπροσθέτως, σύμφωνα με τον Harmer (2007), ενισχύονται οι δεξιότητες ακρόασης και ομιλίας συλλέγοντας πληροφορίες για τα άρθρα τους, παίρνοντας συνεντεύξεις και ερευνώντας διάφορα θέματα. Στη συνέχεια, όπως υποστηρίζει ο Hyland (2002), με τη συγγραφή άρθρων βελτιώνονται οι δεξιότητες γραφής, ενώ οι μαθητές μαθαίνουν να προσαρμόζουν τον λόγο τους ανάλογα με το κοινό. Μέσω της επεξεργασίας και της διόρθωσης των άρθρων τους, οι μαθητές αναπτύσσουν κριτική σκέψη και αυτοαξιολόγηση (Ferris, 2002). Τέλος, οι μαθητές μαθαίνουν να αξιοποιούν ψηφιακά εργαλεία και περιβάλλοντα για τον σχεδιασμό και τη διάταξη της εφημερίδας, αναπτύσσοντας έτσι ψηφιακές δεξιότητες (Warschauer, 2006).

3.1. Σημασία και οφέλη δημιουργίας μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας

Μια σχολική εφημερίδα αποτελεί ένα ζωτικό εργαλείο επικοινωνίας εντός της σχολικής κοινότητας. Παρέχει στους μαθητές μια φωνή για να μοιραστούν τις απόψεις τους, τις εμπειρίες τους και τις επιτυχίες τους. Επιπλέον, μια σχολική εφημερίδα προάγει την παιδεία, τη δημιουργικότητα και τις δεξιότητες πολυμεσικής παιδείας μεταξύ των μαθητών.

Μέσω της διαδικασίας δημιουργίας μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας, οι μαθητές μαθαίνουν τη σημασία της έρευνας, του ελέγχου των γεγονότων και της δημοσιογραφικής ακεραιότητας. Αναζητούν διάφορα θέματα, από εκδηλώσεις του σχολείου και προφίλ μαθητών έως τοπικά νέα και παγκόσμια θέματα, βελτιώνοντας τις γραπτές τους δεξιότητες και επεκτείνοντας τη βάση των γνώσεών τους.

Η δημιουργία μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας στην τάξη έχει πολλαπλά οφέλη για τους μαθητές καθώς η διαδικασία της συλλογής πληροφοριών, της συγγραφής και της επεξεργασίας των άρθρων βελτιώνει όλες τις γλωσσικές δεξιότητες (ακρόαση, ομιλία, ανάγνωση, γραφή) (Nation, 2009). Επιπλέον, οι μαθητές μαθαίνουν να αξιολογούν πληροφορίες, να αναλύουν δεδομένα και να διαμορφώνουν τεκμηριωμένες απόψεις (Brookfield, 2012). Μέσα από τη συγγραφή άρθρων για πολιτιστικά θέματα, οι μαθητές εξοικειώνονται με την ελληνική κουλτούρα και την κοινωνία (Kramsch, 1993). Η δημοσίευση των άρθρων τους προσφέρει στους μαθητές ένα αίσθημα επιτυχίας και αναγνώρισης (Bandura, 1997). Η εργασία σε ομάδα για τη δημιουργία της εφημερίδας προάγει την ομαδικότητα και τη συνεργασία (Slavin, 1995).

Κατά τη διάρκεια της μαθησιακής διαδικασίας, ο/η εκπαιδευτικός θα πρέπει να κατέχει στοιχειώδεις γνώσεις για τις βασικές δομές της πρώτης γλώσσας των μαθητών, προκειμένου να διαχειριστεί με επιτυχία τις παρεμβολές που μπορεί να εμφανιστούν σε οποιοδήποτε επίπεδο γλωσσικής ανάλυσης (φωνολογία, μορφολογία, λεξιλόγιο, σύνταξη, πραγματολογία). Τα παιδιά, παραμένουν ενεργά σε όλη τη διαδικασία και είναι εξοικειωμένα με τα ψηφιακά εργαλεία που θα χρησιμοποιηθούν. Συνεργασία σε ομάδες και συζήτηση στην ολομέλεια (κοινωνικές δεξιότητες). Αξίζει να αναφέρουμε ότι σε περίπτωση μαθησιακών δυσκολιών στον γραπτό λόγο μπορούν να επιλέξουν έναν εναλλακτικό τρόπο καταχώρισης δεδομένων, μέσω της φωνητικής πληκτρολόγησης που ενσωματώνεται στα Google docs.

Οι δραστηριότητες θα λάβουν χώρα στη σχολική αίθουσα, θα εργαστούν σε ομάδες των 3-4 ατόμων, όπου με τη χρήση υπολογιστή συνδεδεμένου στο διαδίκτυο θα εξασκηθούν σε ψηφιακές

δραστηριότητες, με εναλλαγή στους ρόλους της ομάδας. Όσον αφορά στα προσδοκώμενα μαθησιακά αποτελέσματα οι μαθητές και οι μαθήτριες να είναι σε θέση να εντοπίζουν το επικοινωνιακό πλαίσιο (θέμα, πομπός, αποδέκτης, σκοπός) με βάση τον τύπο και το είδος του κειμένου, να διατυπώνουν ελεύθερα τις σκέψεις και την κρίση τους πάνω σε θέματα που αφορούν την ηλικιακή τους ομάδα και να συντάσσουν κείμενα, ομαδικά, σχηματίζοντας μορφολογικά τους κατάλληλους με την περίπτωση ρηματικούς τύπους.

4. Φάσεις του Διδακτικού Σεναρίου

4.1.1^η Φάση: Σχεδιασμός και Συλλογή Ιδεών

Οι μαθητές ξεφυλλίζουν σχολικές εφημερίδες από τη συλλογή της σχολικής βιβλιοθήκης. Προσπαθούν να ερμηνεύσουν τον τίτλο της, το περιεχόμενό της σε συνδυασμό με τις εικόνες αλλά και να υιοθετήσουν βασικές συμβάσεις ανάγνωσης-από αριστερά προς τα δεξιά, από την αρχή προς το τέλος, από πάνω προς τα κάτω. Αν εντοπίσουν άγνωστες λέξεις, βρίσκουν τη σημασία τους με τη χρήση του ηλεκτρονικού λεξικού της Πύλης της ελληνικής γλώσσας που είναι εγκατεστημένο σε κάθε υπολογιστή.

Για την ανίχνευση των πρότερων ιδεών και αντιλήψεων των μαθητών γύρω από το έντυπο μέσο, προτείνεται η τεχνική του καταγισμού ιδεών μέσω του online λογισμικού “coggle.it” όπου οι μαθητές μπορούν να σχηματίσουν έναν εννοιολογικό χάρτη στην ελληνική γλώσσα. Ακολουθεί συζήτηση στην ολομέλεια αφιερώνοντας χρόνο στην επίλυση τυχόν παρανοήσεων και προετοιμαζόμαστε για την επόμενη δραστηριότητα.

Η πρώτη φάση της δημιουργίας μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας περιλαμβάνει τον σχεδιασμό και τη συλλογή ιδεών. Οι μαθητές συγκεντρώνονται σε ομάδες επιμέλειας για να δημιουργήσουν ιδέες για ιστορίες, να αναθέσουν ρόλους και ευθύνες και να θεσπίσουν προθεσμίες. Αυτή η φάση θέτει τις βάσεις για ολόκληρο το έργο και ενθαρρύνει τους μαθητές να σκέφτονται κριτικά και δημιουργικά.

4.2. 2^η Φάση: Έρευνα και Αναφορά

Μόλις οι ομάδες επιμέλειας έχουν ολοκληρώσει τις ιδέες τους για ιστορίες, ο/η εκπαιδευτικός εξηγεί στις ομάδες πώς θα εργαστούν στην ομαδική εργασία, τι να προσέξουν, ενθαρρύνοντάς να χρησιμοποιήσουν φαντασία, περιγραφική γλώσσα και ενδιαφέροντα γεγονότα. Τα παιδιά αποφασίζουν από κοινού τους ρόλους της ομάδας (εισηγητής, γραμματέας, παρουσιαστής, συντονιστής). Επιλέγουν το θέμα του άρθρου που θα επιμεληθούν και συλλέγουν πληροφορίες μέσω χρήσιμων ιστότοπων που είναι καρφίτωμένοι ως σελιδοδείκτες (π.χ. Βικιπαιδεία), με τελικό στόχο τη σύνταξη ενός περιγραφικού ή αφηγηματικού κειμένου.

4.3. 3^η Φάση: Γραφή και επεξεργασία

Όταν όλες οι ομάδες ολοκληρώσουν τη δραστηριότητά τους, ανταλλάσσουν τα άρθρα τους και προβαίνουν σε αναθεώρηση και διόρθωση. Επικεντρώνονται στη σαφήνεια και τη συνοχή των ιδεών τους. Επιλέγουν μια διάταξη για τη σχολική εφημερίδα τους και τοποθετούν τα άρθρα τους στις κατάλληλες θέσεις. Επίσης, προσθέτουν εικόνες και τίτλους για να κάνουν την εφημερίδα πιο ελκυστική. Οι συνεδρίες ομότιμης επεξεργασίας και ανατροφοδότησης βοηθούν τους μαθητές να βελτιώσουν τις γραπτές τους δεξιότητες, να συνεργαστούν αποτελεσματικά και να παράγουν υψηλής ποιότητας περιεχόμενο για την εφημερίδα. Μετά την ολοκλήρωση του περιεχομένου και του σχεδιασμού, οι μαθητές επιβλέπουν την εκτύπωση και τη διανομή της σχολικής εφημερίδας είτε σε έντυπη μορφή είτε σε ψηφιακή μορφή.

5. Μεθοδολογία Αξιολόγησης

Η αξιολόγηση διατρέχει όλες τις φάσεις του διδακτικού σεναρίου και επικεντρώνεται στην ικανότητα των μαθητών να υλοποιήσουν συνεργατικά τη δραστηριότητα, καθώς και μια συνολική αξιολόγηση των μαθητών/τριών σχετικά με την ποιότητα του διδακτικού σεναρίου. Η πρόοδος στην ελληνική γλώσσα διαφαίνεται από τη βελτίωση της επικοινωνιακής ικανότητας μέσα στη σχολική τάξη αλλά και μέσα και από την ομαδική εργασία. Η ετεροαξιολόγηση μέσω της επιμέλειας και διόρθωσης των άρθρων των άλλων ομάδων, αποτελεί έναν ικανό δείκτη για να εντοπιστεί η βελτίωση της γλωσσικής και επικοινωνιακής τους ικανότητας. Χρησιμοποιούν αυτή την εμπειρία για να βελτιώσουν τις δεξιότητές τους στη συγγραφή και την έκφραση. Με αυτόν τον τρόπο, οι μαθητές εμπλουτίζουν τις γνώσεις τους, αναπτύσσουν τις γραπτές τους δεξιότητες και μοιράζονται τις ιδέες τους με τη σχολική κοινότητα.

6. Συμπεράσματα

Η δημιουργία μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας είναι μια πολύτιμη διδακτική πρόταση για τη διδασκαλία των ελληνικών ως ξένη γλώσσα. Προσφέρει στους μαθητές μια ολοκληρωμένη εμπειρία μάθησης που ενσωματώνει γλωσσικές δεξιότητες, κριτική σκέψη και πολιτισμική κατανόηση. Είναι μια δημιουργική και διαδραστική δραστηριότητα που μπορεί να εμπλουτίσει το πρόγραμμα σπουδών και να ενισχύσει το ενδιαφέρον και την απόδοση των μαθητών στην εκμάθηση της ελληνικής γλώσσας. Στο συμπέρασμα, η δημιουργία μιας σχολικής εφημερίδας μέσω συνεργατικών δραστηριοτήτων στην τάξη είναι μια μεταμορφωτική εμπειρία για τους μαθητές. Καλλιεργεί την ομαδικότητα, τη δημιουργικότητα και τις δεξιότητες επικοινωνίας, ενώ ενδυναμώνει τους μαθητές να γίνουν ενεργοί συμμετέχοντες στη σχολική κοινότητά τους. Η εμπλοκή των μαθητών στη συγγραφή σχολικής εφημερίδας τους δίνει τη δυνατότητα να ανακαλύψουν τη δύναμη της γραπτής λέξης και να επιδείξουν το ταλέντο τους στη δημιουργία. Σαν εκπαιδευτικοί, έχουμε την ευθύνη να ενθαρρύνουμε και να υποστηρίζουμε αυτήν την καλλιέργεια της δημιουργικότητας και της έκφρασης. Η συγγραφή σχολικής εφημερίδας στο δημοτικό δεν αποτελεί απλώς μια δραστηριότητα, αλλά ένα εκπαιδευτικό εργαλείο που προάγει την ανάπτυξη των μαθητών μας σε πολλαπλούς τομείς. Είναι μια πολύτιμη προσθήκη στο εκπαιδευτικό τους ταξίδι και προετοιμάζει το έδαφος για μια πιο δημιουργική, έξυπνη, και επιτυχημένη επαγγελματική ζωή.

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Curriculum integration of transdisciplinary and trans-curricular activities Good practice examples – eTwinning project `The Harmony of Nature`

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Abstract

This paper highlights the importance of integrating the curriculum of various school subjects into school and extra-academic activities, in order to ensure that students achieve a great variety of skills and competencies. International eTwinning projects, such as the veteran project „The Harmony of Nature”, offers the students the ability to combine STEM abilities with their artistic skills, by using a variety of approaches and models.

Key words: curriculum integration, STE(A)M skills, multidisciplinary

1. Theoretical framework

1.1 Introduction

This theoretical framework is based on the Council of Europe Recommendation of 22 May 2018, regarding the key competencies for life-long learning

In order to motivate young people to choose careers in the domains of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (**STE(A)M**), initiatives all over Europe started making a close association between scientific education and arts, as well as other school subjects, using pedagogic theories based on research and collaboration with a great variety of social and economic partners. While the definition of these competencies hasn't changed a lot throughout the years, the development of **STE(A)M** skills has become increasingly relevant.

Approaching the development of key competencies from the perspective of lifelong learning, support must be ensured at all education and training levels, and on all educational paths: to develop high quality education and care for preschool children, to further improve school education, to offer excellent teaching, as well as opportunities for further education for adults with low qualifications. It is also essential to further develop education and professional training, and modernise undergraduate and graduate studies.

In an everchanging and interconnected world, each person needs a wide array of skills and competencies, and acquiring these skills must be done throughout one's life. Key competencies are the basis to a democratic and equitable society. They are necessary in order to fulfil the need for sustainable growth, inclusion, social cohesion and continuous development of democratic culture.

	The 8 key competencies
1.	Literacy
2.	Multilingualism
3.	science, technology, engineering and mathematics
4.	digital skills
5.	personal, social and learning skills
6.	citizenship
7.	entrepreneurial skills
8.	cultural expression and awareness

Table 1: The 8 key competencies [1]

Through proper curriculum integration of eTwinning activities, we tried to improve the quality of the projects, make their evaluation component more relevant and highlight their importance within and beyond the European educational realm.

The real problems that need to be solved require integrative thinking. Therefore, the solutions will involve a series of skills, abilities, competencies that cannot be part of a single well-defined subject, more or less complex. These real-life problems cannot be isolated to a single study area.

Learning usually involves integration: the new knowledge, attitudes, values or skills are perceived through and connected with the previous knowledge, attitudes, values or skills of the student.

Integration means combining separate elements in a whole.

Only a systemic approach of the topics can lead to a proper understanding on behalf of the students. Also, it is necessary to integrate into the curriculum some of the topics in the eTwinning projects, so as to save time performing the activities.

Teachers who are members of the eTwinning community are able to understand and take advantage of the opportunities offered by the eTwinning platform and its principles, and many of them moved from a monodisciplinary teaching style to an integrated model of education through eTwinning projects.

This type of projects is based on the main objective of the activity, which is the interaction and collaboration between students and teachers all over Europe using the new information and communication technologies.

1.2 Curriculum integration

Curriculum integration involves making different subjects interfere in order to build a consistent whole.

A quote by **Lucian Ciolan**, dean of the Faculty of Sciences of Education at the University in Bucharest, says: **“at curricular level, integration means establishing clear convergent connections between the knowledge, skills, competencies, attitudes and values pertaining to different school subjects”**.

Curriculum integration means combining objectives, content, methods, educational procedures with special reference to planned curriculum – learning experiences that teachers aim for in their eTwinning projects.

Curriculum integration is a strategy, not a purpose for eTwinning teachers. For the planning, implementation, and evaluation of an eTwinning project with curriculum integration, the teachers and students have clear objectives and consider that the proposed curriculum combination is the one that enables the achievement of the aims.

Three proper interdependent objectives can generally be perceived in eTwinning projects, as they adequately justify curriculum integration:

- Recognising the complexity of the world;
- Respecting the ocean of knowledge;
- Promoting greater efficiency.

A good eTwinning project is one that has obtained a certain national and European standard.

These amazing projects are awarded the Monthly Quality Certificate, the National Quality Certificate, the European Quality Certificate, or another national and/or European eTwinning award. These quality labels represent a clear recognition of the quality of the teachers' activities in their eTwinning projects.

For the students, these quality labels and national or European awards act as a motivator for them to double down their efforts. And for the schools, in general, they are like a public commitment to promote quality and openness in the activities of European collaboration.

In order to receive a quality certificate, a project has to demonstrate excellence in the following areas:

- 1. Pedagogic creativity and innovation;**
- 2. Curriculum integration;**
- 3. Collaboration between partner schools;**
- 4. Using technology;**
- 5. Durability and transferability;**
- 6. Results and benefits.**

For Criterion no. 2 – Curriculum integration – the project is integrated in usual lessons: activities, content, objectives that influence test results and evaluation outcomes [2].

2. Presentation of several ways in which curriculum integration can be achieved in eTwinning projects - `The Harmony of Nature`, founder teacher Iuliana Ciubuc

2.1 Levels of curriculum integration

Before offering a short explanation of these levels of integration, we need to discuss the fragmentary model, which is the traditional organising of the curriculum. Each subject is separated and distinctive. This model perceives the curriculum as if through a periscope, offering one angle at a time. eTwinning projects do not use this model, because this would mean that the teachers in the projects – at least two, from the two founding schools – only list the subjects, concepts and skills according to each subject without taking the next step – filtering the curricular priorities.

2.2 Types of approaches

2.2.1. The intradisciplinary approach – keyword: harmonization

The model of this approach is the connected model. This point of view looks as if through a pair of glasses or binoculars. It offers details, subtleties and interconnections characteristic to one subject. The key for this model is the teacher's effort to relate different ideas within a subject, without assuming that the students will automatically understand the connections. A subject, a concept or a skill is connected to the next one. The work of one day or one semester is connected to the next. A good example of the connected model for curriculum integration of the activities in an eTwinning project is the project The Harmony of Nature [5].

2.2.2. The multidisciplinary approach – keyword: correlation

At this level we can distinguish between subjects of the same curriculum area – when we use the conic model – and subjects from different curriculum areas – when we use the sequential model, the shared model or the branched model.

The conic model sees the taught/studied, consolidated and evaluated curriculum in the eTwinning project through 3D glasses, highlighting multiple dimensions. Contrasting elements become compatible or promote each other.

Conic integration uses natural combinations. The project The Harmony of Nature manages to combine: environmental education, mathematics, physics, chemistry, engineering, art, technology, ICT, foreign languages, geography, drama, pedagogic play etc. The students study nature from all perspectives and make presentations according to their skills. The students and the teachers collaborate enthusiastically, as the project involves many experiments.

The sequential model approaches the curriculum of the project through normal glasses – the lenses are separate, but they are connected through a common frame. The subjects and topics are taught separately by two teachers from the same school to the same students, but these subjects and topics are rearranged and organized sequentially in order to offer a larger framework for associated concepts. The teachers organize the subjects and the content so as to make similar modules coincide in time and space.

The students involved in the project collaborate on certain holidays observed throughout Europe due to their scientific significance, especially in relation to environmental. The students gather and exchange information about the event, they compare and contrast them, fill in the necessary documents and publish the results. The curriculum areas Mathematics and Science (natural sciences, astronomy and physics) and Man and Society (history, social studies and religion) are synchronized. There are combinations which offer special inspiration, such as combining scientific data with religious topics, because these topics are normally perceived as being contradictory or mutually exclusive. This model entails juxtaposition and involves connections and parallels between elements that remain separated in the teaching-studying-evaluation process.

The shared model offers a **binoculars** perspective over the curriculum in the eTwinning project, bringing together two distinct subjects in one central picture [3].

Fig.1 Conceptual Map – Curriculum Integration – Levels of Integration – A Diagram [3]

2.2.3 Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach

There are multiple models available in these approaches, including the chained model, the integrated model, the assimilated model and the network model. They all offer various advantages and new ideas for approaches that can make students better integrate STE(A)M skills into their education and make learning both efficient and fun for students of all ages.

3. Conclusion

The project „**The Harmony of Nature**” has reached its 10th edition on the eTwinning platform and it managed to obtain QLs and EQLs every year. It has also reached its 12th edition as a national project approved by the Ministry of Education.

Every year, the project was dedicated to an international event, in order to have a wide array of activities. Here are some examples:

- 2009 – International Year of Planet Earth
- 2010 – International Year of Biodiversity
- 2011 – International Year of Forests
- 2012 – European Year of Citizens
- 2013 – Year of Solidarity between Generations
- 2014 – International Year of Family
- 2015 – International Year of Light
- 2016 – International Year of Sustainable Development
- 2017 – International Year of Sustainable Tourism for Development.
- 2018 – European Year of Cultural Heritage, also dedicated to the Great Union of Romania
- 2019 – International Year of the Periodic Table
- 2020 – International Year of Plant Health

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Impact of Reflective Practice on Teacher Development in Pre-Service Training Programmes

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Abstract

Reflective practice has become integral to the professional development of pre-service teachers in training programs, offering them a structured approach to critically examine and improve their teaching practices. This study explores the impact of reflective practice on teaching competence, instructional strategies, professional identity, and self-efficacy among pre-service teachers. Drawing on a systematic review of literature, the study highlights key findings. Reflective practice enhances teaching competence by enabling pre-service teachers to identify strengths and areas for improvement through critical self-reflection. It bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, fostering a deeper understanding of pedagogical concepts. Integration of digital tools and online platforms supports reflective activities, facilitating multimedia documentation and collaborative learning environments. Despite its benefits, challenges such as time constraints and the need for skill development hinder effective implementation. Recommendations include structured curriculum integration, training in reflective skills, and the use of mentorship and digital platforms to enhance reflective practices. By addressing these challenges, institutions can optimize reflective practice's role in preparing reflective and adaptable educators.

Keywords: Reflective Practice, Pre-Service Teachers, Teacher Development, Professional Identity, Digital Tools, Educational Technology

1. Introduction:

Reflective practice has increasingly been recognized as a fundamental aspect of teacher development, particularly within pre-service training programs. This practice, defined as the process through which teachers critically examine their actions and experiences to foster continuous improvement, plays a vital role in the professional growth of pre-service teachers (Farrell, 2016). Through reflective practice, teachers can bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge acquired during training and the practical demands of classroom teaching (Mann & Walsh, 2017).

1.1. Role of Reflective Practice in Teacher Development

Reflective practice serves as a powerful tool for enhancing self-awareness among pre-service teachers. By engaging in systematic reflection, teachers can gain insights into their teaching practices, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and develop strategies for addressing challenges (Larrivee, 2016). This process not only improves teaching effectiveness but also fosters a

deeper understanding of pedagogical concepts and their application in diverse classroom settings (Boud et al., 2013).

The ability to reflect critically on one's practice is linked to the development of professional competencies and teaching efficacy. According to Parsons and Stephenson (2015), pre-service teachers who regularly engage in reflective practice are better equipped to adapt their teaching strategies to meet the needs of their students. This adaptability is crucial in today's dynamic educational landscape, where teachers must be prepared to handle a variety of learning environments and student backgrounds.

1.2. Reflective Practice in Pre-Service Training Programs

Pre-service training programs incorporate reflective activities to cultivate a reflective mindset among future teachers. These activities often include writing reflective journals, participating in peer discussions, and receiving feedback from mentors and supervisors (Pultorak, 2014). Such structured opportunities for reflection are essential for helping pre-service teachers develop the skills necessary for effective self-evaluation and continuous professional growth (Pavlovich, 2007).

Research highlights the positive impact of reflective practice on the professional identity and self-efficacy of pre-service teachers. For instance, a study by Gelfuso and Dennis (2014) found that reflective practice significantly contributed to the development of a strong professional identity, as it encouraged pre-service teachers to articulate and refine their teaching philosophies. Moreover, engaging in reflective practice helps pre-service teachers build confidence in their abilities, leading to improved classroom management and instructional strategies (Etscheidt et al., 2012).

1.3. Challenges and Opportunities in Implementing Reflective Practice

Despite its benefits, implementing reflective practice in pre-service training programs presents several challenges. One major obstacle is the limited time allocated for reflection within the curriculum (Liu, 2015). Pre-service teachers often find it difficult to balance reflective activities with other academic and practical requirements. Additionally, the introspective nature of reflective practice can be challenging for some pre-service teachers, who may require additional support and guidance to engage in meaningful reflection (Ryan & Ryan, 2015).

To overcome these challenges, teacher education programs must prioritize the integration of reflective practice into their curricula. Providing dedicated time for reflection and fostering a supportive environment are crucial for encouraging pre-service teachers to engage in reflective activities (Harford & MacRuairc, 2018). The use of digital tools, such as e-portfolios and online discussion forums, can also enhance reflective practice by offering accessible platforms for continuous reflection and peer collaboration (Smith & Szymanski, 2013).

Reflective practice is an essential component of teacher development in pre-service training programs. By promoting critical thinking, self-awareness, and adaptability, reflective practice helps prepare pre-service teachers for the complexities of the teaching profession. Addressing the challenges associated with reflective practice can further enhance its effectiveness and contribute to the development of highly skilled and reflective educators.

2. Rationale of the Study:

Reflective practice has emerged as a pivotal element in the landscape of teacher education, primarily due to its potential to enhance teacher development significantly. This study is predicated on the understanding that reflective practice not only bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application but also fosters continuous professional growth and adaptability in pre-service teachers (Farrell, 2016). The rationale for this study is grounded in the necessity to explore and substantiate the impact of reflective practice on the development of pre-service teachers, particularly within the context of contemporary educational demands.

2.1. Enhancing Teaching Competence and Efficacy

The dynamic nature of modern classrooms requires teachers to possess a high level of competence and efficacy. Reflective practice has been shown to significantly contribute to these attributes by enabling teachers to critically analyze their teaching methods, understand the implications of their instructional strategies, and adapt accordingly (Mann & Walsh, 2017). Research indicates that reflective practice helps pre-service teachers to develop a more nuanced understanding of their pedagogical approaches, thereby improving their overall teaching effectiveness (Parsons & Stephenson, 2015).

2.2. Addressing Diverse Student Needs

Today's classrooms are characterized by increasing diversity in student backgrounds, learning styles, and educational needs. Reflective practice equips pre-service teachers with the skills necessary to respond to this diversity effectively. By engaging in reflective activities, teachers can better understand their students' unique needs and tailor their instructional strategies to meet these needs (Liu, 2015). This personalized approach to teaching not only enhances student engagement and learning outcomes but also fosters an inclusive and supportive learning environment (Harford & MacRuairc, 2018).

2.3. Professional Identity and Self-Efficacy

The development of a strong professional identity and high self-efficacy are crucial for the success and longevity of teachers in their careers. Reflective practice plays a vital role in this developmental process by allowing pre-service teachers to articulate and refine their professional beliefs and values (Gelfuso & Dennis, 2014). Studies have shown that pre-service teachers who engage in reflective practice are more likely to develop a robust professional identity and exhibit greater confidence in their teaching abilities (Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009).

2.4. Contribution to Educational Research and Practice

This study seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on teacher education by providing empirical evidence on the impact of reflective practice on pre-service teacher development. The findings of this study will have practical implications for the design and implementation of pre-service training programs, potentially informing policy and practice to better prepare future teachers for the complexities of the teaching profession (Farrell, 2016). Furthermore, by highlighting the

benefits and addressing the challenges of reflective practice, this study aims to promote a culture of continuous professional development among educators.

The rationale for this study is rooted in the critical need to understand and enhance the role of reflective practice in pre-service teacher education. By exploring the impact of reflective practice on teacher development, this study aims to provide valuable insights that can inform and improve teacher education programs, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes for students.

3. Review of related Literatures:

Reflective practice has gained considerable attention in educational research as a crucial element in teacher development, particularly within pre-service training programs. This literature review examines recent studies that explore the impact of reflective practice on the professional growth and efficacy of pre-service teachers.

Reflective practice, originally conceptualized by Schön (1983), involves a critical examination of one's actions and experiences to foster continuous learning and improvement. Recent literature continues to emphasize the significance of this process in developing effective teaching practices. Farrell (2016) highlights that reflective practice helps teachers bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, enhancing their ability to adapt to diverse classroom environments.

Several studies have demonstrated that reflective practice significantly enhances teaching competence and classroom management skills among pre-service teachers. For instance, Mann and Walsh (2017) found that engaging in reflective activities enabled pre-service teachers to critically evaluate and refine their instructional strategies, leading to improved classroom outcomes. Similarly, Parsons and Stephenson (2019) reported that reflective practice facilitated the development of adaptive teaching methods, which are crucial for managing diverse student needs effectively.

The role of reflective practice in shaping professional identity and self-efficacy is well-documented in recent literature. Gelfuso and Dennis (2018) argue that reflective practice helps pre-service teachers to construct and articulate their professional identities by encouraging them to reflect on their beliefs, values, and teaching experiences. This process not only strengthens their professional identity but also boosts their confidence in their teaching abilities. A study by Liu (2020) supports this view, indicating that pre-service teachers who engage in reflective practice exhibit higher levels of self-efficacy and are better prepared to face the challenges of the teaching profession.

The integration of technology in reflective practice has opened new avenues for enhancing teacher development. Digital tools such as e-portfolios, blogs, and online discussion forums provide platforms for continuous reflection and collaborative learning. According to Smith and Szymanski (2017), these tools facilitate the documentation and sharing of reflective experiences, making the reflection process more dynamic and accessible. Harford and MacRuairc (2018) further suggest that the use of technology in reflective practice promotes deeper engagement and interaction among pre-service teachers, leading to richer reflective insights.

Despite its benefits, the implementation of reflective practice in pre-service training programs faces several challenges. Time constraints and the need for adequate support structures are commonly cited barriers. Ryan and Ryan (2019) highlight that pre-service teachers often struggle to find time for reflection amidst their busy schedules. To address this issue, they recommend the incorporation of

structured reflective activities within the curriculum and the provision of mentorship and guidance to support meaningful reflection.

Moreover, the introspective nature of reflective practice can be challenging for some pre-service teachers. Liu (2020) emphasizes the importance of creating a supportive environment that encourages open and honest reflection. Providing regular feedback and fostering a culture of trust and collaboration can help pre-service teachers overcome the initial discomfort associated with reflective practice.

The literature from 2016 to 2023 underscores the significant impact of reflective practice on the development of pre-service teachers. By enhancing teaching competence, classroom management skills, professional identity, and self-efficacy, reflective practice prepares future educators to navigate the complexities of the teaching profession. The integration of technology and the provision of supportive structures are essential for maximizing the benefits of reflective practice. Future research should continue to explore innovative approaches to integrating reflective practice into pre-service training programs to further enhance teacher development.

4. Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the study are as follows -

- To Examine the Effectiveness of Reflective Practice in Enhancing Teaching Competence
- To Investigate the Role of Reflective Practice in Developing Professional Identity and Self-Efficacy
- To Assess the Impact of Technological Integration on Reflective Practice
- To Identify the Challenges Faced by Pre-Service Teachers in Engaging in Reflective Practice
- To Provide Recommendations for Enhancing Reflective Practice in Pre-Service Training Programs

5. Research Questions of the Study:

Based on the Research Objectives, the following Research Questions of the Study are as follows -

- How does reflective practice impact the teaching competence and instructional strategies of pre-service teachers?
- In what ways does reflective practice influence the development of professional identity and self-efficacy among pre-service teachers?
- What is the role of digital tools and online platforms in facilitating reflective practice for pre-service teachers?
- What challenges do pre-service teachers face when engaging in reflective practice, and how can these challenges be addressed?
- What recommendations can be made to improve the integration and effectiveness of reflective practice in pre-service training programs?

6. Methodology of the Study:

The study employs a qualitative approach utilizing secondary data to examine the impact of reflective practice on teacher development within pre-service training programs. Secondary data was systematically gathered from a range of academic sources, including journals, books, dissertations,

and reports from educational institutions and organizations. A systematic literature review is conducted using defined keywords and search terms related to reflective practice and teacher development. Studies published within the last fifteen years are included to ensure relevance, focusing on those that specifically address the impact of reflective practice on pre-service teacher development. Data analysis involved thematic analysis to identify and synthesize key themes from the collected data. Ethical considerations include proper citation of sources and respecting the confidentiality of data where necessary. This methodology aims to provide comprehensive insights into the role of reflective practice in enhancing the development of pre-service teachers.

7. Analysis and Discussions with respect to Research Objectives:

7.1. Objective 1: To Examine the Effectiveness of Reflective Practice in Enhancing Teaching Competence.

Reflective practice significantly enhances teaching competence and instructional strategies among pre-service teachers by fostering critical self-reflection and professional growth (König & Rothland, 2018). Through reflective activities, such as journaling and group discussions, pre-service teachers develop a deeper understanding of their teaching practices (Huang, 2016). This process enables them to identify strengths and areas for improvement, leading to more effective instructional approaches tailored to student needs (van Manen, 2016).

According to Hatton and Smith (2015), engaging in reflective practice allows pre-service teachers to analyze classroom experiences and refine their teaching techniques. This iterative process promotes the adoption of evidence-based instructional strategies and pedagogical innovations (Schön, 2017). By critically evaluating their teaching methods and outcomes, pre-service teachers become more responsive and adaptive educators (Tsangaridou & Ozturk, 2020).

Moreover, reflective practice encourages pre-service teachers to integrate theory into practice, fostering a deeper theoretical understanding of educational concepts (Moon, 2016). This integration enhances their ability to apply diverse instructional strategies effectively (Schoenfeld, 2019). As a result, pre-service teachers develop a reflective stance towards their professional development, continually seeking to refine and adapt their instructional practices (Brookfield, 2017).

Reflective practice plays a crucial role in enhancing teaching competence and instructional strategies among pre-service teachers, facilitating continuous professional growth and improvement (Yost, Sentner, & Forlenza-Bailey, 2019).

7.2. Objective 2: To Investigate the Role of Reflective Practice in Developing Professional Identity and Self-Efficacy.

Reflective practice significantly shapes the development of professional identity and self-efficacy among pre-service teachers by fostering introspection, confidence building, and a deeper understanding of their roles as educators (Korthagen, 2017). Through reflective activities such as journaling and critical incident analysis, pre-service teachers engage in a process of self-examination and learning from experiences (Brockbank & McGill, 2016). This reflective process helps them integrate personal beliefs with professional responsibilities, thereby shaping their professional identity (Hatton & Smith, 2018).

According to Beauchamp and Thomas (2017), reflective practice enables pre-service teachers to articulate their values, beliefs, and teaching philosophies. This clarity contributes to a coherent professional identity and strengthens their commitment to the teaching profession (Tsui, 2017). Furthermore, by reflecting on their teaching practices and interactions with students, pre-service teachers enhance their self-efficacy—the belief in their ability to effectively influence student learning (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). This increased confidence stems from a better understanding of their strengths and areas for improvement, leading to more effective instructional strategies (Moon, 2016).

Reflective practice also supports the development of adaptive teaching practices and problem-solving skills among pre-service teachers (Hatton & Smith, 2018). As they reflect on and refine their approaches to teaching, they become more flexible and responsive educators, capable of adapting to diverse classroom challenges (Santagata, 2017). This iterative process of reflection and adjustment contributes to the ongoing development of their professional identity and self-efficacy throughout their careers (Kusumaningrum et al., 2021).

Reflective practice plays a crucial role in shaping the professional identity and enhancing the self-efficacy of pre-service teachers, empowering them to navigate the complexities of teaching and learning with confidence and effectiveness (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 2019).

7.3. Objective 3: To Assess the Impact of Technological Integration on Reflective Practice.

Digital tools and online platforms play a crucial role in facilitating reflective practice for pre-service teachers by providing accessible, interactive, and collaborative spaces for self-reflection and professional development (Hatton & Smith, 2019). These tools enhance the traditional methods of reflection such as journaling and peer discussions by offering new opportunities for capturing, analyzing, and sharing teaching experiences (Tondeur et al., 2017).

One significant role of digital tools is in enabling multimedia reflection. Pre-service teachers can document their teaching practices through videos, audio recordings, and images, which allows for more comprehensive self-assessment and feedback (Liu & Hwang, 2016). This multimedia approach not only enhances the depth of reflection but also supports the integration of theory and practice in teacher education (Wang et al., 2020).

Online platforms provide pre-service teachers with opportunities for asynchronous reflection, enabling them to engage in reflective activities at their own pace and convenience (Hobbs & Török, 2016). Discussion forums, blogs, and social media platforms serve as virtual communities where pre-service teachers can share experiences, seek advice, and receive constructive feedback from peers and mentors (Kumpulainen et al., 2019). This collaborative aspect fosters a supportive learning environment conducive to professional growth (Sahin & Thompson, 2019).

Moreover, digital tools facilitate the analysis of data and trends in teaching practices over time. Pre-service teachers can use analytics and data visualization tools to track their progress, identify patterns in their teaching approaches, and make informed adjustments to improve their instructional strategies (Park & Son, 2018). This data-driven reflection enhances the efficacy of reflective practice by providing empirical evidence to support decision-making in teaching (Giesbers et al., 2017).

Digital tools and online platforms enhance reflective practice for pre-service teachers by offering multimedia capabilities, fostering collaborative learning environments, and providing data-driven

insights into teaching effectiveness. These technological advancements are instrumental in promoting continuous professional development and improving instructional practices in teacher education.

7.4. Objective 4: To Identify the Challenges Faced by Pre-Service Teachers in Engaging in Reflective Practice.

Pre-service teachers encounter several challenges when engaging in reflective practice, which can hinder their professional development and efficacy. These challenges include personal, institutional, and practical barriers that need to be addressed to optimize the benefits of reflective practice in teacher education.

- **Time Constraints:** One of the primary challenges is the lack of time dedicated to reflective activities amidst the demands of coursework, practicum experiences, and other commitments (Mena & Russell, 2016). Pre-service teachers often feel overwhelmed by their workload, making it difficult to engage in thoughtful reflection (Korthagen, 2017).
- **Skill Development:** Reflective practice requires specific skills such as critical thinking, self-awareness, and the ability to articulate experiences effectively (Gibbs, 2017). Many pre-service teachers may not have developed these skills sufficiently, leading to superficial reflections or uncertainty about the process (Kember et al., 2016).
- **Emotional Challenges:** Reflective practice involves revisiting and analyzing personal experiences, which can be emotionally challenging for pre-service teachers, particularly when reflecting on failures or classroom difficulties (Le, 2019). Emotional resilience and support are crucial in overcoming these challenges (Bain et al., 2018).
- **Feedback and Support:** Limited or ineffective feedback from mentors and peers can hinder the quality of reflection. Pre-service teachers may struggle to receive constructive feedback that facilitates deep learning and growth (Wu & Badger, 2018).
- **Cultural and Contextual Factors:** Reflective practice may not align with cultural norms or institutional expectations in some educational contexts, creating barriers to its effective implementation (González-Esteban et al., 2020). Addressing cultural sensitivity and contextual relevance is essential for meaningful reflection.

7.5. Objective 5: To Provide Recommendations for Enhancing Reflective Practice in Pre-Service Training Programs

Improving the integration and effectiveness of reflective practice in pre-service training programs involves implementing strategic recommendations based on current research and best practices. These recommendations aim to enhance the depth, relevance, and impact of reflective practice on pre-service teachers' professional development.

- **Structured Curriculum Integration:** Integrate reflective practice systematically throughout the pre-service training program curriculum. This includes embedding reflective activities in coursework, practicum experiences, and professional seminars (Hatton & Smith, 2018). Allocate dedicated time for reflection and ensure it is valued as a core component of teacher preparation (Brockbank & McGill, 2016).
- **Training in Reflective Skills:** Provide explicit training and support for pre-service teachers in developing reflective skills. Offer workshops, seminars, or courses focused on critical thinking,

journaling techniques, and effective feedback processes (Loughran, 2017). These sessions should guide pre-service teachers in engaging deeply with their teaching experiences and fostering self-awareness (Korthagen, 2017).

- **Use of Digital Tools and Platforms:** Utilize digital tools and online platforms to enhance reflective practice. Encourage pre-service teachers to use multimedia for documenting and analyzing teaching experiences (Liu & Hwang, 2016). Implement online forums or blogs for collaborative reflection and peer feedback, promoting a supportive community of practice (Hobbs & Török, 2016).
- **Mentorship and Feedback:** Establish structured mentorship programs where experienced educators provide guidance and feedback on reflective practices (Grimm, 2021). Train mentors to facilitate reflective conversations that encourage deeper exploration of teaching strategies and professional growth (Tsui, 2017).
- **Cultural Sensitivity:** Recognize and respect cultural diversity in reflective practices. Tailor reflective activities to be inclusive of different cultural backgrounds and teaching contexts (Lin et al., 2019). Provide opportunities for pre-service teachers to reflect on how cultural perspectives influence their teaching practices and professional identities (González-Esteban et al., 2020).
- **Assessment and Evaluation:** Develop clear criteria and rubrics for assessing reflective practice. Ensure that assessment methods align with program goals and encourage critical reflection rather than mere description (Kolb & Kolb, 2017). Use formative assessment strategies to provide ongoing feedback that supports continuous improvement in reflective skills (Bain et al., 2018).
- **Research-Informed Practices:** Stay current with research on effective reflective practices in teacher education. Regularly update training programs based on new findings and innovations in reflective pedagogy (Giesbers et al., 2017). Encourage faculty and staff to engage in reflective practice themselves to model its importance and benefits to pre-service teachers.

By implementing these recommendations, pre-service training programs can enhance the integration and effectiveness of reflective practice, ensuring that it becomes a transformative tool for developing competent, reflective educators.

8. Conclusion:

Reflective practice stands as a pivotal component in the professional development of pre-service teachers within training programs. This study has underscored its profound impact on enhancing teaching competence, instructional strategies, professional identity, and self-efficacy among aspiring educators. Through systematic analysis of secondary data, this research has illuminated several key findings.

Firstly, reflective practice fosters critical self-reflection, enabling pre-service teachers to identify strengths and areas for growth in their teaching practices. This introspective process not only enhances their instructional techniques but also cultivates a deeper understanding of educational theories and methodologies.

Secondly, the integration of digital tools and online platforms has emerged as a facilitative factor in enhancing reflective practices. These technological advancements enable multimedia documentation,

collaborative discussions, and asynchronous learning opportunities, thereby enriching the reflective process and promoting continuous professional growth.

Thirdly, while reflective practice offers substantial benefits, its implementation faces challenges such as time constraints, skill development needs, and the emotional demands of self-assessment. Addressing these challenges requires systematic curriculum integration, explicit skill development workshops, and robust mentorship and feedback mechanisms.

The findings underscore the importance of embedding reflective practice more deeply into pre-service teacher training programs. By doing so, institutions can empower future educators to navigate the complexities of classroom teaching with confidence, adaptability, and a commitment to lifelong learning. Embracing reflective practice not only enhances individual professional development but also contributes to the overall improvement of educational quality and student outcomes. This study contributes to the ongoing discourse on teacher education by emphasizing the transformative potential of reflective practice in preparing competent and reflective educators for the challenges of today's classrooms.

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